

Odonata surveys 2010–2016 in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman, with emphasis on some regional heritage species

Philippe Lambret^{1,2,9}, Jean-Pierre Boudot^{2,3}, David Chelmick⁴,
Geert De Knijf⁵, Éric Durand⁶, Jacky Judas⁷ & Anthony Stoquert⁸

¹Tour du Valat, Research Institute for the Conservation of Mediterranean Wetlands, Le Sambuc, 13200 Arles, France; <lambret@tourduvalat.org>

²Société Française d'Odonatologie, 7 rue Lamartine, 78390 Bois-d'Arcy, France;

³Immeuble Orphée, Apt 703, 78 rue de la Justice, 54710 Ludres, France;
<jean.pierre.boudot@numericable.fr>

⁴Macromia Scientific, 31 High Beech Lane, Haywards Heath RH16 1SQ, UK;
<david.chelmick@gmail.com>

⁵Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Kliniekstraat 25, 1070 Brussels, Belgium; <geert.deknijf@inbo.be>

⁶Château Vilain RN7, 13410 Lambesc, France; <mr.oizo3@gmx.fr>

⁷Emirates Wildlife Society – WWF, PO Box 454891, Dubai, United Arab Emirates;
<jjudas@ewswwf.ae>

⁸56170 Hoedic, France; <anthony.stoquert@gmail.com>

⁹coordinator, corresponding author

Received 25th August 2017; revised and accepted 3rd November 2017

Abstract. Six field trips were carried out in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and the Sultanate of Oman in autumn 2010, late winter 2013, spring 2014, autumn 2014, spring 2015 and spring 2016. We recorded 37 species at 87 localities, including new localities for some species of regional interest. Information on all observed Odonata species was recorded including their life stage, behaviour, habitat and water characteristics. Exuviae were also systematically collected. *Urothemis thomasi* was discovered at several new sites in the Hajar Mountains, the Dhofar and the Al Wusta regions, filling in the gap between the Dhofar and the Muscat area. In addition, new localities for two Arabian endemics: *Arabicnemis caerulea* and *Arabineura khalidi* were found, with their occurrence in the Dhofar region extending their known area and demonstrating that *A. khalidi* cannot be regarded as a strict Hajar endemic. Important differences were noticed in the species composition of formerly surveyed localities, which may be ascribed to habitat degradation through management directed towards human recreation. Lastly, the well-known and diverse zoogeographical influences of Omani and the Emirati odonatofauna are confirmed with a large set of species of African origin in the Dhofar and a smaller set of species of Indomalayan origin visiting both the

Dhofar and the northeast of the region during migrations and establishing, at least temporary, reproductive localities.

Further key words. Dragonfly, damselfly, Anisoptera, Zygoptera, Arabian Peninsula, Hajar Mountains, Dhofar, Red List, *Arabicnemis caerulea*, *Arabineura khalidi*, *Azuragrion somalicum*, *Azuragrion nigradorsum*, *Agriocnemis pygmaea*, *Paragomphus sinaiticus*, *Orthetrum ransonnetii*, *Tholymis tillarga*, *Urothemis thomasi*, *Macrodiplax cora*.

Introduction

The dragonfly fauna of the Sultanate of Oman and of the United Arab Emirates has already been subject to several studies (SCHNEIDER 1988; WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; GILES 1998; FEULNER et al. 2007; VAN DER WEIDE & KALKMAN 2008; REIMER et al. 2009; WIPRÄCHTIGER 2010; COWAN & COWAN 2013, 2015; BALL 2014; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). Data are not only available in scientific literature but, more recently, have been published on ‘citizen science’ web databases such as ‘www.observation.org’ and various internet galleries and forums. However, due to the enormous extent of desert areas and to the limited development of the former road network, data are not regularly spatially distributed, leaving large areas without information. Although slightly more than 3000 records are available from *ca* 537 localities in Oman and the UAE, almost 91 % of these locations provided records of less than 10 species, with an average of only two species (J.-P. Boudot unpubl. data). As the Odonata fauna of desert and semi-desert regions may vary rapidly according to rainfall variation at both a seasonal and annual level, some discoveries may be expected. On the one hand, *Urothemis thomasi* Longfield, 1932 was observed for the first time in the UAE on 10-vi-2013 in Wadi Wurayah National Park (FEULNER & JUDAS 2013); however, the present distribution and life history of this species remains poorly known and its conservation status has been evaluated as »Endangered« according to the IUCN red list of threatened species (BOUDOT 2006), emphasizing the need of additional research. On the other hand, the regional distribution of species such as *Agriocnemis pygmaea* (Rambur, 1842), *Azuragrion somalicum* (Longfield, 1931), *Paragomphus sinaiticus* (Morton, 1929) and *Orthetrum ransonnetii* (Brauer, 1865) is only partly known and whether species such as *Macrodiplax cora* (Kaup in Brauer, 1867), *Tramea basilaris* (Palisot de Beauvois, 1817) and *T. limbata* (Desjardins, 1832) are reproducing or consist only of migrants, remains unclear.

In this study, we present the result of fieldwork from the years 2010–2016 in the region, with an emphasis on poorly known species.

Material and methods

Abbreviations

UAE – United Arab Emirates; WWNP – Wadi Wurayah National Park.

Initials of authors

AS – Anthony Stoquert; DC – David Chelmick; ÉD – Éric Durand; GDK – Geert De Knijf;

JJ – Jacky Judas; JPB – Jean-Pierre Boudot; PL – Philippe Lambret.

This study is based on a total of six independent surveys conducted in the years 2010 to 2016. Two surveys were performed by ÉD in November 2010 and in February–March 2013 in 29 localities including 23 in the Dhofar region. Following the discovery of *U. thomasi* in 2013, the WWNP research team under the coordination of JJ attempted to clarify the status and distribution of *U. thomasi*, seeking to gather information on its ecological requirements that might further support conservation initiatives. In addition, several odonatological surveys were conducted through the Hajar Mountains of the UAE and Oman and in the Dhofar area of Oman, where the type locality is situated. Other independent surveys were executed by GDK in April 2014 and March–April 2016, by JPB, DC and PL in October–November 2014 and by JPB, PL and AS in March–April 2015. The objectives of the surveys were to gain a better understanding of the species richness and abundance of the regional Odonata fauna and to clarify especially the distribution of *U. thomasi*. This encompassed a characterisation of its habitat including physical and chemical parameters as well as surveying the geographical range where the species was suspected to occur, namely within the Hajar Mountains and the Dhofar as well as in the intermediate Al-Wusta region.

Investigated localities and sampling effort

Preliminary selection of study sites was made by visiting previously surveyed localities (Fig. 1), by identifying potentially interesting new sites using Google Earth or by visiting localities known for their natural and avian diversity (cf. SARGEANT et al. 2008). Localities were named using their local names and numbered from the North to the South (Figs 2, 3 and 4). Their coordinates (decimal degrees, WGS84 datum) and elevation (meters

above sea level [m a.s.l.]) were determined with a hand held GPS and were compiled together with the relevant date and the corresponding observers' names and, in most cases, investigation duration. The amount of time spent on each locality was dependent upon its size, fragmentation, structure complexity, ecological interest and odonate diversity as well as the personal choice of the survey leaders.

Figure 1. General map of Odonata records for the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman. Red dots indicate records taken during our surveys 2010–2016, black dots indicate records from other studies. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

Figure 2. Map of localities visited during our surveys 2010–2016 in the Hajar Mountains, United Arab Emirates and Sultanate of Oman. Locality numbers correspond to those given in the result section. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

Figure 3. Map of localities visited during our surveys 2010–2016 in the Al Wusta region and the empty quarter of Dhofar, Sultanate of Oman. Locality numbers correspond to those given in the result section. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

Habitat description

To describe the various habitats (Fig. 5), the main features of every locality have been noted. Important physical characteristics (temperature [°C], conductivity [mS/cm] as a proxy of salinity and pH) were measured with an Oakton® Waterproof Multiparameter PCS TESTR 35 logger.

Odonata records

We recorded species present at each locality together with their life stage (adults, exuviae, larvae, emergents, teneral and immatures) and indices of reproduction (tandem, copula, oviposition). At most of the sites exuviae were collected and labelled with respect to the sampling site and date. These have subsequently been identified by DC and are presently stored in his private collection. It is intended that the exuviae will eventually be donated in part to the British Museum (Natural History) in London and the remainder to an appropriate natural history society or museum in the UAE/Oman. The exuviae of many species from this region have not yet been described in detail. In this paper DC has researched the literature and, based on the work of this survey, has been able to outline reliable identification features for all anisopteran species (CHELMICK et al. 2016). The situation with Zygoptera is not as clear-cut, as very little work has been done on their larval stages. DC has based his identifications on his own observations of exuviae and larvae studied at Wadi Wurayah.

Figure 4. Map of localities visited during our surveys 2010–2016 in the coastal part of Dhofar, mainly in the Salalah area, Sultanate of Oman. Locality numbers correspond to those given in the result section. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

Results

Visited localities

United Arab Emirates

Ras Al Khaymah north

Loc. 1. Ras el Kaïmah, Wadi Bih (25.79555°N, 56.07912°E, 112 m a.s.l.): 17-x-2014 (1 h, PL).

Pools of standing water. Pool: *ca* 20×40 m, water depth unknown; bottom: mud; no vegetation.

Fujayrah north

Loc. 2. Dahir, Wadi Al Lahbah.

Site 1 (25.54494°N, 56.15483°E, 265 m a.s.l.): 15-x-2014 (3 h 30 min, PL).

Wadi with pools fed by resurgences. Pool 1: *ca* 3×15 m, max. water depth 0.6 m; bottom: mud and stones; vegetation: algae and dead shoots. Pool 2: *ca* 1×2 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: stones; vegetation: algae and dead leaves.

Site 2 (25.54987°N, 56.15707°E, 293 m a.s.l.): 15-x-2014 (1 h, PL). Wadi with pools and stream fed by resurgences. Pool: *ca* 1×15 m; bottom: mud; no vegetation; water features: unavailable.

Loc. 3. Abadilah, Wadi Abadilah (25.43981°N, 56.19921°E, 308 m a.s.l.): 16-x-2014 (6 h, PL).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool 1: *ca* 2×7 m, max. water depth 0.6 m; bottom: mud and stones; vegetation: algae and dead leaves, banks with grasses. Pool 2: *ca* 3×4 m, max. water depth 0.5 m; bottom: mud and rocks; vegetation: algae and dead shoots.

Loc. 4. Zubara, Wadi Wurayah (25.39598°N, 56.26931°E, 211 m a.s.l.): 09–11-x-2014 (13 h, PL); 11-iv-2015 (1 h, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi with stream and replenished pools. Pool above the waterfall (Fig. 6a): *ca* 1×15 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: none within, bordered by *Phragmites* on one side. Pool downstream of gorges: *ca* 5×15 m, max. water depth 1.2 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: algae and banks with *Phragmites*. Pool above the gorges and below a narrow pass: *ca* 2×5 m, water depth 0.05–0.5 m; bottom: sand, gravel and stones; no vegetation.

Loc. 5. Masafi, Al Khulaybiyah (25.36455°N, 56.18823°E, 527 m a.s.l.): 16-x-2014 (1 h, PL).

Pool of standing water colonized by algae; *ca* 1.5×7 m, max. water depth 0.18 m.

Sharjah

Loc. 6. Masafi, Wadi Shees (= Shis) above Shees village (25.29316°N, 56.24420°E, 430 m a.s.l.): 11-x-2014 (2 h, PL).

Narrow wadi with running water and retention pools (for irrigation network [falaj] supply; Fig. 5a). Downstream retention pool: *ca* 10×30 m, max. water depth 0.1 m; bottom: mud and stones; no vegetation; water features: unavailable. Retention for water supply: *ca* 6×10 m, max. water depth 1 m; bottom: stones; vegetation: algae and dead shoots; water features: unavailable.

Loc. 7. Madha, Wadi Al Madha (25.30733°N, 56.27528°E, 299 m a.s.l.).

Wadi with pools and streams fed by resurgences. 11-x-2014 (2 h, PL): Pool 1: *ca* 10×10 m, max. water depth 1.5 m; bottom: mud, sand and stones; vegetation: algae and dead shoots. 13-x-2014 (6 h, PL): Pool 2: *ca* 2×3 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; no vegetation. Pool 2: *ca* 1×1 m, max. water depth 0.4 m; bottom: gravel; vegetation: *Saccharum*.

Fujayrah south

Loc. 8. Hayl, Wadi Ham dam (25.13555°N, 56.29474°E, 64 m a.s.l.): 16-x-2014 (5 min, PL).

Dry. No Odonata recorded.

Ras Al Khaymah south

Loc. 9. Harrah, Wadi Helo (25.01988°N, 56.20843°E, 478 m a.s.l.): 21-x-2014 (1 h, PL).

Dry concrete retention basin within a private garden: *ca* 5×7 m; vegetation: algae.

Loc. 10. Huwaylat city (24.88109°N, 56.16576°E, 213 m a.s.l.): 21-x-2014 (15 min, PL).

Man-made, concrete retention basin within a private garden, *ca* 3×4 m.

Dubai

Loc. 11. Hatta (24.79436°N, 56.11965°E, 343 m a.s.l.).

Site 1: 19-x-2014 (1 h, PL): Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: *ca* 4×20 m, max. water depth unknown; bottom: mud, gravel and rocks; helophytes only in upstream pool.

Site 2: 21-x-2014 (30 min, PL; Fig. 5b): Pool of turbid standing water: *ca* 20×50 m, vegetation: *Phragmites*.

Sultanate of Oman

Al Dhahira

Loc. 12. Ar Rayy, Wadi Al Qhafi (24.64464°N, 56.11271°E, 549 m a.s.l.): 20–21-x-2014 (1 h, 1 h, PL).

Wadi with stream and replenished pools of *ca* 10×50 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: gravel and stones; vegetation: none. Pool: *ca* 1×3 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: gravel and stones; vegetation: algae and dead shoots.

Loc. 13. Mahdha, Subaitah oasis (24.26553°N, 56.16133°E, 733 m a.s.l.): 20-x-2014 (3 h, PL).

Retention basin as a water supply for downstream plantations (Fig. 5c); *ca* 10×20 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom and edges: concrete; vegetation: algae. Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: *ca* 2×7 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: gravel and stones; vegetation: algae.

Loc. 14. Yanqul, Sayyah (23.69178°N, 56.54793°E, 737 m a.s.l.): 25-x-2014 (1 h 30 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi with hypercaline spring and headwater (pH = 11.77 in upper course, shifting towards pH = 9 some hundreds meters downstream). Pools replenished by slow running water, many with white deposits and flocculates mainly of calcium carbon-

ate (calcite, aragonite) and magnesium hydroxide (brucite) in both the wadi bed (and its adjacent falaj) and in the water (cf. CHAVAGNAC et al. 2013a). Such white flocs and deposits originate from the sequestration of the atmospheric carbon dioxide by the hypercaline water (pH = 11–12) and its reaction with the pre-existing aqueous calcium and magnesium. The basicity of the spring water is largely due to the serpentinisation of the surrounding ultramafic rocks minerals (serpentinised ophiolites/gabbro/peridotites) and the oxidation of their ferrous iron (cf. CHAVAGNAC et al. 2013b). Pool: ca 1×5 m, bottom: gravel and stones; vegetation: algae. White pool (Fig. 5d): ca 1×5 m, bottom: white deposits; no vegetation.

Al Batinah

Loc. 15. Shinas, Wadi Khamis (= 'Hatta pools') (24.75005°N, 56.19168°E, 289 m a.s.l.): 19-x-2014 (2 h 15 min, PL).

Wadi with stream and replenished pools. Pool: ca 6×6 m, max. water depth 0.8 m; bottom: gravel, stones and rocks; no vegetation.

Loc. 16. Liwa, Fazah (24.51425°N, 56.46283°E, 104 m a.s.l.): 28-x-2014 (1 h 30 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: ca 3×20 m, max. water depth 0.4 m; bottom: mud and stones; vegetation: algae, helophytes (Juncaceae/Cyperaceae), banks with *Tamarix* sp. and tall grasses.

Loc. 17. Saham, Hayl Ra'sah (= Wadi Al-Surami) (23.93307°N, 56.72137°E, 321 m a.s.l.).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool, 28-x-2014 (3 h 30 min, DC/JPB/PL): ca 2.5×12 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: algae, banks with grasses. Stream, 10-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS): bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: banks with grasses.

Loc. 18. Al Khabourah, Ghuzayn (23.79356°N, 56.97042°E, 215 m a.s.l.): 24-x-2014 (2 h, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi (running water) with few pools. Stream: max. width 3 m, max. water depth 0.1 m; bottom: stones; vegetation: none. Pool: ca 1×5 m, max. water depth 0.2 m; bottom: mud and gravel; vegetation: hydrophytes.

Loc. 19. Al Khabourah, Ghab.

Site 1: 24-x-2014 (1 h, DC/JPB/PL). Wadi with replenished pools (23.70715°N, 56.90887°E, 422 m a.s.l.). Pool: ca 3×15 m, max. water depth 0.25 m; bottom: sand and gravel; vegetation: banks with *Phragmites* and dead leaves.

Site 2: 24-x-2014 (30 min, DC/JPB/PL). Open air cistern (23.69101°N, 56.91784°E), ca 6×10 m, supplied by a falaj; bottom: mud, edges: concrete, vegetation: algae and helophytes.

Site 3: 25-x-2014 (2 h, DC/JPB/PL): Wadi with replenished pools. Pool 1 (23.65874°N, 56.93268°E): ca 1×1.5 m, max. water depth 0.2 m; bottom: gravel and stones; vegetation: algae and dead leaves, banks with grasses. Pool 2 (23.65749°N, 56.93456°E): ca 1.5×5 m, max. water depth 0.5 m; bottom: mud, stones and rocks; vegetation: dead leaves and banks with grasses.

Loc. 20. Rustaq, Hajir (23.54373°N, 57.20851°E, 389 m a.s.l.): 27-x-2014 (45 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi pool managed to supply a falaj: ca 10×40 m, max. water depth 1 m; bottom: gravel, stones and rocks; vegetation: none. Downstream pool: ca 1×4 m.

Loc. 21. Rustaq, Hawqayn (23.53048°N, 57.32967°E, 247 m a.s.l.): 26-x-2014 (5 h, DC/JPB/PL); 30-iii-2015 (2 h, JPB/PL/AS).

Stony wadi at Al Mamora ford and upstream. Wadi with replenished pools fed by running water from main stream. Pool 1: ca 0.8×1 m, max. water depth 0.1 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: algae and dead leaves, banks with grasses. Terrace above wadi with well-vegetated shallow pools fed by running water coming from above plantations and direct rock seepages. The largest pool was grassy and flooded in autumn, dry in spring. Pool 2: ca 4×10 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: algae and *Typha*.

Loc. 22. Iqd an Nizuh (23.47969°N, 57.29855°E, 365 m a.s.l.): 26-x-2014 (1 h, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi with occasionally replenished pools. The wadi was used as a road joining small villages. Pipework construction was being carried out at the time of the survey. Pool: ca 5×5 m, max. water depth 0.6 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: helophytes.

Loc. 23. Rustaq, Rustaq hot spring, Ayn al Kasfah (23.39324°N, 57.41149°E, 361 m a.s.l.): 19-iv-2014 (GDK), 27-x-2014 (15 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Hot spring: ca 7×4 m, max. water depth 4 m; bottom: rocks; no vegetation. Most species however were observed at the outflow channel with abundant bank vegetation within 100 m of the hot spring.

Loc. 24. Rustaq, At Tabaqah (23.38371°N, 57.30713°E, 469 m a.s.l.): 27-x-2014 (30 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Running water and pools of apparent poor ecological quality, with numerous trash heaps and roadworks within the wadi upstream of the study site; bottom: stones; vegetation: algae, dead leaves and unidentified sedges.

Loc. 25. Al Far, Wadi Bani Auf.

Site 1 (23.29027°N, 57.4676°E, 710 m a.s.l.): 19-iv-2014 (1 h, GDK). Intermittent running water with sections of fast-flowing and nearly standing water before seeping away in the dry river bed.

Site 2 (23.30383°N, 57.47753°E, 364 m a.s.l.): 19-iv-2014 (45 min, GDK). Falaj of 0.7 m width along the dry river-bed with fast flowing water shaded by palm trees.

Loc. 26. Al Awabi, Wadi Abyad (23.44056°N, 57.66756°E, 250 m a.s.l.): 30-iii-2015 (15 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi was dry during the visit. Investigations took place around a nearby falaj.

Ad Dakhliyah

Loc. 27. Al Hamra, Qilal (23.39612°N, 57.20527°E, 529 m a.s.l.). 27-x-2014 (2 h, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: ca 3×6 m, max. water depth 0.25 m; bottom: sand and gravel; vegetation: banks with grasses. 10-iv-2015 (1 h, JPB/PL/AS): Falaj, wadi being dry.

Loc. 28. Al Hamra, Ad Dif (23.39145°N, 57.21840°E, 511 m a.s.l.): 27-x-2014 (30 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: ca 20×30 m, max. water depth 1.5 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: banks with grasses.

Loc. 29. Al Hamra, Al Khadra (23.36684°N, 57.30742°E, 516 m a.s.l.): 27-x-2014 (15 min, DC/JPB/PL).

Wadi of apparent poor ecological quality, at the time of the visit being used as a road for construction work of an underground pipework.

Loc. 30. Jebel Shams.

Site 1 (23.23717°N, 57.14897°E, 1 446 m a.s.l.): 18-iv-2014 (15 min, GDK). Misfah city, temporary pool in the wadi, bottom muddy and stony, some scattered bushes nearby.

Site 2 (23.17177°N, 57.15305°E, 837 m a.s.l.): 18-iv-2014 (30 min, GDK). Ar Ruhbah city, temporary pools within the wadi, bottom muddy and stony, some scattered bushes nearby.

Loc. 31. Bahla, Ar Rissah (23.07120°N, 57.36807°E, 656 m a.s.l.): 09-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Pond replenished by a spring which rises from the mountain, ca 15×50 m, max. water depth 0.6 m; bottom: mud and stones, hydrophytes.

Loc. 32. Bahla city (22.96157°N, 57.29639°E, 545 m a.s.l.): 09-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi with replenished pool, ca 15×100 m, max. water depth 0.25 m; bottom: mud and stones; vegetation: banks with *Phragmites* and *Typha*.

Loc. 33. Nizwa, Farq (22.88453°N, 57.52295°E, 482 m a.s.l.): 21-ii-2013 (ÉD). Falaj by private palm grove.

Loc. 34. Al Ulyah, Wadi Bani Kharous (23.1803°N, 57.64658°E, 889 m a.s.l.): 19-iv-2014 (2 h, GDK).

Wadi, several meters wide, bottom mud and stones; abundant bank vegetation of grasses, *Phragmites*, and shrubs in a palm grove valley.

Muscat – Capital Area

Loc. 35. As Seeb, Muscat international airport (23.58678°N, 58.29034°E, 15 m a.s.l.): 21-ii-2013 (ÉD).

Artificial basin partially covered by algae.

Loc. 36. As Seeb, Ghala Industrial Estate (= Ghala as Sinaiyah), at highway exit (23.56705°N, 58.33813°E, 55 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2014 (1 h, GDK).

Some ponds located in an industrial excavated site with some bushes.

Loc. 37. Muttrah, Al Qurum park (23.61664°N, 58.48431°E, 1 m a.s.l.): 06-xi-2010 (ÉD). Series of artificial and permanent ponds bordered by green grass, palm trees and shrubs.

Loc. 38. Al Amirat, Wadi Aday (23.54130°N, 58.52519°E, 65 m a.s.l.): 30–31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015 (3 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool 1: ca 2×30 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: banks with *Typha* and grasses, hydrophytes,

moss on stones. Pool 2 (Fig. 6b): ca 25×65 m, max. water depth 0.8 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: banks with *Phragmites* and *Typha*, hydrophytes. Pool 3: ca 50×190 m.; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: banks with *Phragmites* and *Typha*, hydrophytes.

Loc. 39. Quriyat, Wadi Dayqah.

Site 1 (23.08621°N, 58.87938°E, 117 m a.s.l.): Wadi with stream and replenished pools. Stream (07-iv-2015, 1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS): ca 20×130 m, max. water depth 0.5 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: *Typha*. Pool (08-iv-2015, 1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS; Fig. 6c): ca 35×450 m, max. water depth 2 m; mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: hydrophytes (Characeae), helophytes (Juncaceae/Cyperaceae), *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Site 2 (23.13277°N, 58.90115°E, 41 m a.s.l.): 26-iii-2016 (3 h, GDK). Due to a flash-flood a week prior to the visit, the river was >10 m wide and flowing fast, with rocky bottom and bank. The deeper parts consisted of huge, deep pools, hundreds of meters long and 80 m wide; banks muddy, almost no vegetation present.

Loc. 40. Quriyat, Dibab; Wadi Al Arbaieen (= Al Arbiyyin) (23.07558°N, 59.02802°E, 13 m a.s.l.): 07-iv-2016 (45 min, GDK).

Wadi consisting only of remnant pools. Bottom muddy, banks muddy and stony with small parts of grasses and rushes.

Ash Sharqiyah

Loc. 41. Tiwi, Wadi Ash Shab (22.83828°N, 59.24428°E, 20 m a.s.l.): 07-iv-2014 (5 h, GDK), 27-iii-2016 (6 h, GDK), 07-iv-2016 (4 h, GDK).

This wadi was surveyed almost from its mouth upstream for a distance of nearly 3 km. The lower part comprised a very broad lagoon of 100×400 m fringed on one side by grasses, bushes and a palm grove. Upstream, in the canyon, the river was moderately flowing with locally standing water stretches. The water was very clear, (Fig. 5e). Its width varied between 2 and 6 m with varying deeper (>3 m) and shallow parts with small rocks and large boulders, running through a green valley with shrubs, palm trees and grasses.

Loc. 42. Tiwi, Wadi Tiwi. The river was reduced to isolated pools with only minor flow between them.

Site 1: Pool near bridge (22.82178°N, 59.25800°E, 20 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2016 (3 h, GDK). Pool of 60×200 m with abundant grassy vegetation (rushes, sedges) and some low bushes. Bottom and banks muddy.

Site 2: Pool 2 (22.80447°N, 59.24568°E, 30 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2016 (3 h, GDK) and slow-flowing river with clear water forming several deeper pools (<2 m). Abundant aquatic and riparian vegetation (grasses, rushes, sedges) with some scattered bushes. Bottom and banks fine gravel, big boulders and rocks.

Site 3: Pool 3 (22.80085°N, 59.24447°E, 35 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2016 (1 h, GDK) and slow flowing river with clear water with only some shallow pools (<1 m) in the river. Bank vegetation of bushes and some scattered grasses. Bottom and bank: sand and big boulders.

Loc. 43. Wadi Bani Khalid.

Site 1 (22.61842°N, 59.09338°E, 650 m a.s.l.): 09-iv-2014 (1 h 30 min, GDK), 28-iii-2016 (3 h, (GDK). Complex of river, falaj, some pools and marshy area with abundant riparian vegetation (grasses, sedges, rushes, *Phragmites*) and with *Potamogeton* present in some pools. Situated beneath a tourist complex and a well-known local swimming spot.

Site 2 (22.60548°N, 59.08870°E, 613 m a.s.l.): 08-iv-2014 (2 h, GDK), 28-iii-2016 (30 min, GDK). Pool of 25×60 m with abundant riparian (grasses, sedges, rushes, *Phragmites*) and partly aquatic vegetation in 2014. It had a high structural diversity with shallow and deeper parts.

Site 3: Mugal (22.59980°N, 59.08107°E, 605 m a.s.l.): 09-iv-2014 (45 min, GDK). Eutrophic pool in dry riverbed with lots of algae. Bank on one side with gravel stones and other site bordered by the village palm grove.

Loc. 44. Sayk (Fig. 6d) (22.50550°N, 59.13058°E, 372 m a.s.l.): 07-iv-2015 (1 h 40 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi with replenished pools. Pool: ca 10×70 m, max. water depth 2 m; bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Loc. 45. Sur, Wadi Musawi (= Wadi Al Fulayj or Wadi Rafsah).

Site 1 (22.46424°N, 59.38771°E, 90 m a.s.l.): 08-iv-2014 (45 min, GDK); 07-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS); 28-iii-2016 (1 h 30 min, GDK). Wadi with replenished pools. Pool (Fig. 6e): ca 20×100 m, max. water depth 2.5 m; mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: hydrophytes (cf. *Potamogeton* sp.), helophytes (Cyperaceae), banks with *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Site 2 (22.51169°N, 59.42339°E, 35 m a.s.l.): 08-iv-2014 (1 h, GDK). Shallow pool of 100×500 m in wadi at road bridge ca 6 km downstream site 1, with very muddy bank and bottom. Isolated stands of rushes with some sparse *Tamarix*.

Loc. 46. Ras al Ruways, Wahiba sands (20.94595°N, 58.78787°E, 16 m a.s.l.): 29-iii-2016 (1 h, GDK).

Wet depression in the sand dunes with some pools (Fig. 5f). Sparse vegetation of *Tamarix* rushes and spiny tickets; bottom: mud.

Al Wusta

Loc. 47. Rumayli, Ayn Najir (20.32789°N, 57.79105°E, 42 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2015 (1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Wadi with brackish running water (salinity = ca 9.27 PSU [“Practical Salinity Unit”]) and with replenished pools. Stream: max. water depth 0.2 m, width = 1 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: Juncaceae. Pool (Fig. 6f): ca 1.5×5 m, max. water depth 0.3 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: algae; earthy banks with salt crusts; banks with short dead *Phragmites*.

Loc. 48. Ras Madrakah, Ras Khushayim (18.97038°N, 57.78562°E, 117 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Lagoon: bottom: mud; no vegetation.

Loc. 49. Quwayrah, Khor Dharif (18.9386°N, 57.34452°E, 1 m a.s.l.): 11-iv-2014 (2 h, GDK), 30-iii-2016 (1 h 30 min, GDK).

Large lagoon (max. 520×1380 m) in the coastal dunes. The upper part contained fresh water but dried out during the summer, the southern part was brackish. Hypertrophic water with abundant algae. Riparian vegetation of very low grasses (overgrazing), rushes and some bushes.

Loc. 50. Haima, Al Ghaftain, water station in the desert along the road 31 southwest of Haima (19.61206°N, 55.40668°E, 116 m a.s.l.): 01-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS). Puddle renewed by leaks from a water pumping station; bottom: mud and sand; vegetation: *Phragmites*.

Dhofar

An area dominated by lime and other calcareous deposits and, in contrast to the Hajar range, without ultramafic rocks. The water is generally soft although moderately alkaline in the karstic springs and wadis and brackish in the lagoons. No hyperalkaline springs in this area.

Loc. 51. Muqshin, Muntasar oasis (19.45358°N, 54.619936°E): 13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013 (ÉD).

Large permanent shallow pools in desert area, vegetation: *Phragmites* and long grasses.

Loc. 52. Muqshin, Qatbit.

Site 1: Hotel (19.17460°N, 54.50344°E, 160 m a.s.l.); 13-xi-2010 (ÉD), 17-iv-2014 (45 min, GDK). Artificial small water basins with concrete bottom, without bank vegetation, situated in a park-like area.

Site 2: Spring (19.15553°N, 54.50805°E, 160 m a.s.l.); 17-iv-2014 (30 min, GDK), 05-iv-2016 (30 min, GDK). Natural spring with dense stands of *Phragmites* and *Tamarix*.

Loc. 53. Thumrait, Dawkah Farm (18.73725°N, 53.99144°E): 23-ii-2013 (ÉD).

Palm trees and sparse shrubs without aquatic habitat but use of fossil water table for agriculture.

Loc. 54. Sharbithat, Khor Sharbithat (17.93480°N, 56.27983°E, 3 m a.s.l.): 06-iv-2015 (30 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Lagoon; bottom: mud; no vegetation.

Loc. 55. Ash Shuwaymiya, Ras Shuwaymiya.

Site 1: Hanging gardens (17.93367°N, 55.52665°E, 109 m a.s.l.): 23-ii-2013 (ÉD), 12-iv-2014 (45 min, GDK). Spring in a large wadi. Pool of 30×30 m just below the waterfall, dry in spring 2014. Some aquatic vegetation present very locally.

Site 2: Wadi (17.91169°N, 55.46609°E, 112 m a.s.l. and 17.90972° N, 55.45737°E, 133 m a.s.l.): 24-ii-2013 (ÉD), 12-iv-2014 (3 h, GDK). Very large wadi (several hundred meters long, >100 m wide. Bottom and banks muddy. Well-developed riparian vegetation (bushes, *Typha*, *Phragmites*, rushes, grasses).

Site 3: Khor (17.88149°N, 55.60302°E, 3 m a.s.l.): 24-ii-2013 (ÉD). Hypertrophic water with abundant algae.

Loc. 56. Hasik, Wadi Sana'ak (17.59861°N, 55.25148°E, 1 m a.s.l.): 23-ii-2013 (ÉD), 05-iv-2015 (1 h 45 min, JPB/PL/AS). Lagoon: ca 50×1 300 m, bottom: mud, gravel and stones; vegetation: hydrophytes, helophytes (Juncaceae/Cyperaceae), banks with *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Loc. 57. Hasik, Natif waterfall (17.47538°N, 55.22967°E, 57 m a.s.l.): 12-iv-2014 (20 min, GDK), 5-iv-2015 (40 min, JPB/PL/AS).

Concrete basin for recreation, fed by a waterfall from an adjacent cliff: ca 10×35 m, max. water depth 0.4 m; bottom: mud; vegetation: *Typha*.

Loc. 58. Sadh, Bandar Bay.

Site 1: Coast 3.6 km NW of Ras Nuss (17.26636°N, 55.24116°E, 23 m a.s.l.), 05-iv-2015 (10 min, JPB/PL/AS). Car park along the coastal road.

Site 2: Coastal wadi and coastal lagoon 4.7 km NW Ras Nuss (17.27575°N, 55.23934°E, 31 m a.s.l.), 26-ii-2013 (ÉD). Permanent pools in a small gorge with sparse vegetation (mainly *Typha* and *Phragmites*) well above a coastal lagoon.

Loc. 59. Sadh, Khor Hadbeen (17.19739°N, 55.21836°E, 6 m a.s.l.): 26-ii-2013 (ÉD). Eutrophic coastal lagoon characterised by abundant algae and heavily grazed pasture.

Loc. 60. Sadh, Khor Mahall (17.09581°N, 55.11676°E, 9 m a.s.l.): 26-ii-2013 (ÉD). Large coastal lagoon with abundant riparian vegetation. Permanent water restricted to the coastal area during the visit.

Loc. 61. Mirbat, Wadi Baqlat (16.96398°N, 54.77902°E, 11 m a.s.l.): 27-02-2013 (ÉD), 04-iv-2016 (GDK).

Muddy coastal lagoon with abundant *Phragmites* and *Typha* vegetation and grassy patches. Little water present.

Loc. 62. Mirbat, Wadi Anshayr, Khor east of Marriott Resort (16.95952°N, 54.74899°E, 5 m a.s.l.). 11-xi-2010 (ÉD), 04-iv-2016 (GDK).

Khor of 70×250 m with many waterfowl present. Abundant riparian vegetation of grasses, sedges, rushes, *Typha* and *Phragmites*. Aquatic vegetation present in large parts of the lagoon.

Loc. 63. Mirbat, Ayn Shabun (17.05335°N, 54.64406°E, 340 m a.s.l.): 03-xi-2014 (1 h, JPB).

Fountain and cisterns in a gorge, dry at the time of the visit. No Odonata recorded.

Loc. 64. Mirbat, Ayn Hashir, (headwater of Wadi Hanna). (17.05402°N, 54.60816°E, 305 m a.s.l.): 27-ii-2013 (ÉD); 16-iv-2014 (30 min, GDK); 07-xi-2014 (30 min, JPB). Concrete dam pond on a headwater brook, ca 10×3 m, stony to rocky, in a Baobab forest. Neither hydrophytes nor helophytes.

Loc. 65. Tayq, Ayn Hut (17.19062°N, 54.55416°E, 827 m a.s.l.): 07-xi-2014 (30 min, JPB).

Stony wadi bed, dry at the time of the visit. No Odonata recorded.

Loc. 66. Taqah, Tawi Atayr (17.11338°N, 54.55936°E, 607 m a.s.l.): 1-iv-2016 (GDK).

Vicinity of a sinkhole containing permanent water.

Loc. 67. Taqah; Khor and beach 12.5 km E of Taqah SSE Kizetakhayf (17.03523°N, 54.52117°E, 10 m a.s.l.): 16-iv-2014 (GDK).

Eutrophic coastal lagoon of 170×30 m characterised by abundant algae. Grassy riparian vegetation alternating with some small patches of rushes.

Loc. 68. Taqah, Wadi Darbat lake and supply stream above the waterfall (between 17.11118°N, 54.45371°E, 205 m a.s.l. and 17.09758°N, 54.45072°E, 197 m a.s.l.): 11-xi-2010 (ÉD), 16-iv-2014 (4 h, GDK), 06-xi-2014 (2 h 30 min, JPB); 4-iv-2015 (2 h, JPB/PL/AS), 01-iv-2016 (6 h, GDK).

In autumn, immediately after the summer monsoon, this area is wet and green with grasslands surrounding the lake (Fig. 5g). Water accumulates in the wadi bed (ca 50×900 m, max. depth 1.5 m). The bottom is muddy and the vegetation comprises hydrophytes and is bordered with trees on one side, with grassland or mud on the other. Size and depth of the supply stream Wadi Darbat change continually according to season and year.

Loc. 69. Taqah, Khor Rawri.

Site 1: Small inlet stream of the lagoon (northern tip) bordered by abundant vegetation of *Typha*, *Phragmites*, *Tamaris*, rushes and grasses. Muddy. (17.05137°N, 54.42582°E, 12 m a.s.l.): 11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013 (ÉD); 13-iv-2014 (1 h, GDK); 04-iv-2016 (2 h, GDK).

Site 2: Lagoon (17.04278°N, 54.42889°E, 4 m a.s.l.): 06-xi-2014 (1 h, JPB), 13-iv-2014 (1 h, GDK). Large lagoon with an obvious salt gradient at mouth of Wadi Darbat as evidenced by the vegetation and salt crusts. Standing water bordered directly by hills to the west, and by a wide muddy, grassy and swampy flat bank on the East.

Loc. 70. Taqah, Khor Taqah (17.03611°N, 54.37500°E, 3 m a.s.l.): 10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013 (ÉD); 13-iv-2014 (1 h 30 min, GDK); 06-xi-2014 (1 h, JPB); 05-iv-2015 (1 h, JPB/PL/AS); 31-iii-2016 (3 h, GDK), 01-iv-2016 (3 h, GDK), 04-iv-2016 (1 h) (GDK).

Lagoon: ca 160×700 m, bottom: mud and sand; vegetation: helophytes (Juncaceae/Cyperaceae), *Typha*, *Phragmites* and *Salicornia*. The fast flowing outflow of the Khor with sandy bottom has a gradient from freshwater to salty towards the sea.

Loc. 71. Taqah, Ayn Athum (17.11842°N, 54.36633°E, 275 m a.s.l.): 07-xi-2014 (10 min, JPB).

Resurgent pool. A temporary subterranean brook piped in a semi open dry concrete falaj over 80 m, then falaj closed and piped underground. Waterfall dry. Site paved completely for recreation, no vegetation.

Loc. 72. Taqah, Khor Sawli (17.04405°N, 54.33035°E, 15 m a.s.l.): 04-iv-2016 (1 h, GDK).

Immense reed-bed on the eastern part, no detectable water during visit.

Loc. 73. Taqah, Ayn Tabraq (17.10031°N, 54.32669°E, 110 m a.s.l.): 07-xi-2014 (45 min, JPB); 04-iv-2015 (3 h, JPB/PL/AS).

Swampy spring and slow-flowing stream supplied by resurgence, partly paved for recreation. Immediately downstream of the spring (Fig. 6g): ca 20×20 m, max. wa-

ter depth 0.2 m; bottom: mud and stones; vegetation: algae, hydrophytes and helophytes, no tall vegetation.

Loc. 74. Taqah, Ayn Hamran (17.09667°N, 54.28100°E, 85 m a.s.l.): 10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013 (ÉD); 14-iv-2014 (1 h 30 min, GDK); 07-xi-2014 (1 h 30 min, JPB); 01-iv-2016 (30 min, GDK).

Paved basin (18×20 m), without vegetation except one tree, apparently situated at a Vauclusian spring. Concreted outflow with rather fast current, shortly channelled, followed by a wild brook between bushes and trees, intermittent after 150 m and ending in a grassy shallow pond *ca* 400 m downstream. In Spring only a short outflow with *Potamogeton* vegetation and then dry. Pond also nearly dry.

Loc. 75. Taqah, Ayn Razat (17.13021°N, 54.23763°E, 115 m a.s.l.): 10-xi-2010 (ÉD); 05-xi-2014 (1 h 30 min, JPB); 31-iii-2016 (2 h, GDK).

Spring in wadi bed, channelled, paved and open over *ca* 400 m, then piped underground. Area largely managed for recreation, neither swampy area nor aquatic vegetation. Type locality of *U. thomasi*.

Loc. 76. Salalah, Ayn Sahalnaut (= Ayn Sahnawt) (17.14822°N, 54.17833°E, 125 m a.s.l.): 16-iv-2014 (GDK); 03-xi-2014 (1 h, JPB).

Large and deep pool (30×18 m), apparently a Vauclusian spring. Almost no hydrophytes, no helophytes. Fast flowing channelled to stony outflow partly piped over 250 m, with a small side puddle, then a wild brook in a wide grassy area over less than 200 m. In spring 2014, this latter part was rather slow flowing.

Loc. 77. Salalah, Khor Ad Dahariz (17.01606°N, 54.17889°E, 2 m a.s.l.): 07-xi-2010 (ÉD).

Long and thin coastal lagoon; water surface mainly open and lined with dense riparian vegetation (*Phragmites*, rushes) and sandy or grassy banks.

Loc. 78. Salalah, Khor Al Baleed, (17.00717°N, 54.14243°E, 4 m a.s.l.): 02-iii-2013 (ÉD).

Lagoon situated in the Al Baleed archeological park. Mainly sanitised with narrow strips of vegetation on banks.

Loc. 79. Salalah, Jarziz farm (17.03317°N, 54.13948°E, 10 m a.s.l.): 12-xi-2010 (ÉD). Large-scale grass cultivation without aquatic habitat.

Loc. 80. Salalah, Ayn Jarziz (17.10700°N, 54.07553°E, 130 m a.s.l.): 05-xi-2014 (30 min, JPB).

Residual temporary pond (*ca* 8×8 m) at resurgence, densely covered with algae. Neither hydrophytes nor helophytes. Resurgence, waterfall and wadi otherwise dry. Most of the site paved for recreation.

Loc. 81. Salalah, “Ayun pools” (17.24889°N, 53.88747°E, 683 m a.s.l.): 05-xi-2014 (3 h, JPB); 03-iv-2015 (1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS); 03-iv-2016 (1 h 30 min, GDK).

Deep permanent pools below cliffs in a gorge in a wadi bed: *ca* 40×300 m, vegetation: helophytes (Juncaceae/Cyperaceae) and deep banks with *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Loc. 82. Salalah, Ayn Ishat (16.99981°N, 53.81897°E, 208 m a.s.l.): 04-xi-2014 (2 h, JPB); 01-iv-2015 (2 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS). Narrow headwater course flowing on

ca 800 m in autumn 2014, reduced to a 100 m stretch and a residual pool in spring 2015. Pool (Fig. 6h): ca 4×7 m, max. water depth 1 m; bottom: mud and rocks (5 %); vegetation: Characeae banks with ferns, *Typha* upstream.

Loc. 83. Salalah, Aftalqut (16.89597°N, 53.8645°E, 85 m a.s.l.): 02-iv-2016 (GDK). Viewpoint on cliffs above sea.

Loc. 84. Salalah, Al Mughsayl, Wadi Madom at Khor Madom (16.89046°N, 53.82307°E, 10 m a.s.l.): 08-xi-2010 (ÉD); 15-iv-2014 (2 h), 02-iv-2016 (3 h, GDK). Large eutrophic coastal lagoon (250×50 m) with abundant algae surrounded by grassy vegetation (Fig. 5h); bottom: sand and mud.

Loc. 85. Salalah, Al Mughsayl, Wadi Ashawq: three residual pools of standing water in Wadi Ashawq with tiny reed-bed and a few trees and bushes, and a coastal lagoon in the continuity of the wadi.

Site 1 (16.89503°N, 53.77402°E, 20 m a.s.l.): 15-iv-2014 (2 h, GDK), 02-iv-2015 (2 h, JPB/PL/AS), 02-iv-2016 (2 h, GDK). Pool ca 20×130 m, bottom: mud; vegetation: banks with *Typha*, *Phragmites*, *Scirpus* and grasses. Dimensions were much smaller in spring 2016.

Site 2 (16.88929°N, 53.77767°E, 13 m a.s.l.): 15-iv-2014 (2 h, GDK), 04-xi-2014 (2 h, JPB), 02-iv-2015 (1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS), 02-iv-2016 (2 h, GDK). Pool ca 40×200 m, max. water depth 4 m; bottom: mud; banks with *Typha* and *Phragmites*.

Site 3 (16.88546°N, 53.78203°E, 10 m a.s.l.): 04-xi-2014 (2 h, JPB), 02-iv-2015 (1 h 30 min, JPB/PL/AS). Pool: ca 50×300 m, bottom: mud; vegetation: banks with large and dense *Typha* and *Phragmites* belt.

Site 4 (16.88109°N, 53.77881°E, 3 m a.s.l.): 01-iii-2013 (ÉD), 15-iv-2014 (GDK), 02-iv-2015 (1 h, JPB/PL/AS). Coastal dune lagoon (ca 40×150 m), grassy banks and islets, many boulders around; bottom: unknown; vegetation: algae, banks with Cyperaceae and grasses.

Loc. 86. Salalah, Shaat, Khor Rass Sajir (16.788846°N, 53.671800°E, 32 m a.s.l.): 01-iii-2013 (ÉD). Wadi with reduced groundwater waterholes during dry period.

Loc. 87. Salalah, Sinkhole Shaat (16.77306°N, 53.58764°E, 847 m a.s.l.): 01-iii-2013 (ÉD). Sinkhole dry during the visit.

Right page – Figure 5. Examples of various habitats encountered during our surveys 2010–2016 in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman. a – concrete falaj at loc. 6. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (11-x-2014); b – pond with muddy water at loc. 11. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (21-x-2014); c – concrete retention basin at loc. 13. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (20-x-2014); d – hyperalkaline pool with white deposits of calcite and Aragonite at loc. 14. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (25-x-2014); e – wadi with both shallow running water and deeper pools at loc. 41. Photo: GDK (07-iv-2016); f – wet depression in the sand dunes at loc. 46. Photo: GDK (29-iii-2016); g – lake supplied by a stream at loc. 68 Photo: GDK (01-iv-2016); h – coastal lagoon (khor) at loc. 84. Photo: GDK (15-iv-2016).

Water characteristics

Waters were rather basic and pH values ranged from 7.05 to 11.77 (mean 8.61, SD 0.73, n = 59; see Appendix 1).

Species observed

The observed species are listed and commented on below with their corresponding identification site numbers. Records are based on adult sighting, more rarely only on exuvia collecting. When available, breeding stadia and behaviour are given in parentheses: lar – larva; ex – exuvia(e); em – emergence; te – teneral; im – immature; tan – tandem; cop – copula; ovi – oviposition. The dates of observation are given in parentheses where locations and sites have been visited more than once.

Platycnemididae

Arabicnemis caerulea Waterston, 1984

Loc. 2-1, loc. 2-2, loc. 3 (ovi), loc. 4 (cop) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014, 28-iii-2015, 12-iv-2015, 15-iv-2015), loc. 7 (ex, tan, ovi), loc. 12 (ovi), loc. 15 (ex), loc. 17 (10-iv-2015), loc. 19-3 pools 1 & 2, loc. 27 (27-x-2014), loc. 34 (ovi), loc. 39-1, loc. 39-2 (ten), loc. 41 (cop, ex, ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-2 (cop, ovi), loc. 43-1 (cop, ex, ovi) (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (cop, ovi) (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 85-1 (ex), loc. 85-2 (02-iv-2015)

Disparoneuridae

Arabineura khalidi (Schneider, 1988)

Loc. 3 (tan), loc. 4 (ex, cop, ovi) (10-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 28-iii-2015, 11-iv-2015, 12-iv-2015, 13-iv-2015), loc. 6 (ex), loc. 7 (im, tan), loc. 11, loc. 12 (ex, ovi), loc. 13, loc. 14 (ovi), loc. 15 (ex, tan), loc. 17 (ex) (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 19-3 pools

Left page – Figure 6. Habitat pictures of localities where *Urothemis thomasi* was recorded during our surveys 2010–2016 in the Sultanate of Oman. a – pool above the waterfall at loc. 4 where a female was ovipositing. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (11-iv-2015); b – loc. 38. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (31-iii-2015); c – loc. 39. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (08-iv-2015); d – loc. 44. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (07-iv-2015); e – loc. 45. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (07-iv-2015); f – pool at loc. 47 where a male was hovering. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (06-iv-2015); g – loc. 73. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (04-iv-2015); h – loc. 82; exuviae were found on emerging dead material just besides the tree on the left. Photo: PL/EWS-WWF (01-iv-2015).

1 & 2 (ex), loc. 21 (ex) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 24, loc. 27 (ex) (27-x-2014 10-iv-2015), loc. 39-1 (te), loc. 41 (ex, cop, ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-2 (ovi), loc. 42-3 (ex, ovi), loc. 43-1 (cop, ovi) (09-iv-2014), loc. 45-1 (cop) (28-iii-2016), loc. 81 (05-xi-2014)

Coenagrionidae

***Azuragrion nigradorsum* (Selys, 1876)**

Loc. 64 (cop, ovi) (27-ii-2013, 16-iv-2014), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 73 (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 85-1 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016)

***Azuragrion somalicum* (Longfield, 1931)**

Loc. 55-1 (ovi, tan) (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 58-2, loc. 81 (03-iv-2015)

***Ischnura evansi* Morton, 1919**

Loc. 2, loc. 3 (ovi), loc. 4 (10-x-2014), loc. 11 (cop), loc. 16 (ex, cop), loc. 17 (28-x-2014), loc. 19-1, loc. 19-3 pool 1, loc. 20, loc. 21 (ex, cop, ovi) (26-x-2014 30-iii-2015), loc. 22, loc. 24, loc. 31 (ex), loc. 35, loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex, ovi) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1 (cop), loc. 41 (cop) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016), loc. 42-2, loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (cop) (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 47 (ex, cop), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 57 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 68 (ex) (14-iv-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013), loc. 70 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 81 (ex, cop) (03-iv-2015), loc. 85-2 (ex) (02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4

***Ischnura senegalensis* (Rambur, 1842)**

Loc. 39-1, loc. 40 (cop), loc. 41 (07-iv-2016), loc. 46, loc. 47, loc. 49 (ovi) (11-iv-2014, 30-iii-2016), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-3 (24-ii-2013), loc. 56 (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-2, loc. 59, loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (ovi) (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2016), loc. 67 (ovi), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (cop, ovi) (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013 02-iii-2013 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016, 01-04-2016, 04-04-2016), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 77, loc. 78, loc. 84 (08-xi-2010, 15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (01-iii-2013, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (te, cop) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015)

***Ceriagrion glabrum* (Burmeister, 1839)**

Loc. 41 (tan), loc. 42-1 (ovi, cop), loc. 43-1 (cop) (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (07-iv-2015), loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013), loc. 55-2 (12-iv-2014), loc. 58-2, loc. 64 (ovi) (27-ii-2013, 16-iv-2014), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (cop) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 73 (tan) (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (07-xi-2014), loc. 76 (03-xi-2014), loc. 81 (03-iv-2015), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 85-1 (02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (02-iv-2015), loc. 85-3 (cop, tan) (02-iv-2015)

***Pseudagrion decorum* (Rambur, 1842)**

Loc. 7, loc. 16 (ovi), loc. 17 (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 37, loc. 38 (cop) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 41 (cop, ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 43-1 (ovi) (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 67, loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013), loc. 69-2 (06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (05-iv-2015), loc. 75 (tan) (31-iii-2015), loc. 76 (03-xi-2014), loc. 85-1 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (cop) (02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (ex of *Pseudagrion* sp.) (02-iv-2015)

***Pseudagrion sublacteum* (Karsch, 1893)**

Loc. 68 (11-xi-2010), loc. 73 (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (cop, ovi) (14-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014)

***Agriocnemis pygmaea* (Rambur, 1842)**

Loc. 70 (te) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 05-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2, loc. 85-4 (01-iii-2013)

Aeshnidae***Anax ephippiger* (Burmeister, 1839)**

Loc. 3, loc. 4 (ex) (29-x-2014), loc. 12, loc. 17 (28-x-2014), loc. 21 (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 33, loc. 35, loc. 37, loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 52-1 (13-xi-2010), loc. 53, loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013), loc. 58-2, loc. 62 (11-xi-2010), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013), loc. 70 (ex) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 05-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 77, loc. 78, loc. 81 (ex) (03-iv-2015), loc. 84 (08-xi-2010), loc. 85-1 (ex), loc. 85-2 (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (01-iii-2013), loc. 87

***Anax imperator* Leach, 1815**

Loc. 2 (ex), loc. 3, loc. 4 (ex, ovi) (10-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 12-iv-2015, 13-iv-2015), loc. 6 (ovi), loc. 7 (ex), loc. 10, loc. 12, loc. 15 (cop), loc. 17 (28-x-2014), loc. 18, loc.

19-1 (ex, ovi), loc. 19-3 pool 1 (ex), loc. 21 (ex, ovi) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 22 (ovi), loc. 24, loc. 27 (ex) (27-x-2014), loc. 28, loc. 31 (ovi), loc. 34 (ovi), loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex, ovi) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1 (ex), loc. 41 (ex, ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1 (ex), loc. 42-2 (ovi), loc. 43-1 (ovi) (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (ovi) (08-iv-2014), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (ex, ten) (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 47, loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 55-1 (ovi) (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 57 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 59, loc. 60, loc. 61 (ovi), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2016), loc. 64 (ex) (16-iv-2016), loc. 67 (ovi), loc. 68 (ex, ovi) (11-xi-2010, 14-iv-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 04-iv-2016), loc. 70 (ex) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016), loc. 73 (ovi) (04-iv-2015), loc. 75 (ovi) (10-xi-2010, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (ovi) (16-iv-2016, 03-xi-2014), loc. 77, loc. 80, loc. 81 (03-iv-2014, 05-xi-2014, 03-iv-2015), loc. 82 (ex) (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 84 (15-iv-2014), loc. 85-1 (ex) (02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (ex) (02-iv-2016), loc. 85-4 (01-iii-2013)

***Anax parthenope* (Selys, 1839)**

Loc. 11, loc. 12 (ovi), loc. 17 (ovi) (28-x-2014), loc. 38 (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014), loc. 45-1 (cop) (08-iv-2014), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013), loc. 57 (05-iv-2015), loc. 59, loc. 68 (06-xi-2014), loc. 73 (04-iv-2015), loc. 77, loc. 85-2 (ovi) (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (02-iv-2015)

Gomphidae

***Lindenia tetrphylla* (Vander Linden, 1825)**

Loc. 17 (10-iv-2015), loc. 38 (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015), loc. 39-1 (ex), loc. 39-2, loc. 41 (ex, tan) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 42-3, loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (ovi) (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 45-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (12-iv-2014), loc. 68 (ex) (11-xi-2010, 14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016)

***Paragomphus genei* (Selys, 1841)**

Loc. 17 (cop) (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18 (ex, em), loc. 25-1, loc. 25-2 (ex), loc. 27 (27-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 41 (27-iii-2016)

***Paragomphus sinaiticus* (Morton, 1929)**

Loc. 3 (ex), loc. 4 (ex) (29-x-2014, 28-iii-2015, 12-iv-2015), loc. 7 (ex), loc. 12, loc. 13 (ex), loc. 14 (ex), loc. 15 (lar, ex), loc. 16 (ex), loc. 17 (ex) (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1 (ex), loc. 19-2 (ex), loc. 21 (ex) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-

-2015), loc. 22, loc. 27 (ex) (27-x-2014), loc. 31, loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015), loc. 41 (ex) (07-iv-2016), loc. 42-2, loc. 42-3 (em, ex), loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 45-1 (07-iv-2015), loc. 55-2 (12-iv-2014), loc. 64 (27-ii-2013), loc. 68 (ex) (14-iv-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 73 (ex) (04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (14-iv-2014), loc. 75 (31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014)

Libellulidae

Crocothemis erythraea (Brullé, 1832)

Loc. 3 (cop), loc. 4 (ex) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 28-iii-2015, 12-iv-2015), loc. 6, loc. 11 (cop), loc. 13 (ex), loc. 16 (ex), loc. 17 (28-x-2014), loc. 18, loc. 19-1 (ex), loc. 19-2 (ex), loc. 19-3 pool 1 (ex), loc. 21 (ex, im, cop) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 23 (19-iv-2014), loc. 24, loc. 28, loc. 30-2, loc. 31 (ex), loc. 32 (cop), loc. 34, loc. 35, loc. 36, loc. 37, loc. 38 (ovi) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 39-2, loc. 40, loc. 41 (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 43-1 (em) (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2016), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (cop) (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 45-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 46, loc. 47, loc. 49 (11-iv-2014, 30-iii-2016), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 52-2 (17-iv-2014), loc. 53, loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (12-iv-2014), loc. 55-3 (24-ii-2013), loc. 56 (23-ii-2013), 57 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-2, loc. 59, loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010), loc. 64 (27-ii-2013, 16-iv-2014), loc. 67, loc. 68 (14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (ex) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016, 01-iv-2016, 04-iv-2016), loc. 71, loc. 73 (cop, ovi) (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (07-xi-2014), loc. 75 (31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 77, loc. 79, loc. 80, loc. 82 (04-xi-2014), loc. 84 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (ex, ovi) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (15-iv-2014)

Crocothemis sanguinolenta (Burmeister, 1839)

Loc. 4 (10-x-2014, 28-iii-2015, 12-iv-2015, 15-iv-2015), loc. 11, loc. 26, loc. 37, loc. 38 (08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 55-1 (12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (12-iv-2014), loc. 58-2, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 64 (07-xi-2014), loc. 68 (01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (13-iv-2014), loc. 70 (13-iv-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 74 (14-iv-2014), loc. 79, loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 84 (15-iv-2014), loc. 85-2

Diplacodes lefebvrri (Rambur, 1842)

Loc. 4 (im, ovi) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014), loc. 11, loc. 21 (ex, cop) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 38 (31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1 (ovi), loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 45-1 (07-iv-2015), loc. 46, loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-

-2013), loc. 52-1 (17-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013), loc. 56 (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-2, loc. 59, loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2016), loc. 67, loc. 68 (14-iv-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (ex, im, cop) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016), loc. 72, loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014), loc. 77, loc. 81 (03-iv-2015), loc. 82 (ex) (01-iv-2015), loc. 84 (08-xi-2010, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (ex, cop) (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (cop) (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (01-iii-2013, 15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015)

***Macrodiplax cora* (Kaup in Brauer, 1867)**

Loc. 46, loc. 49 (cop, ovi, imm) (11-iv-2014, 30-iii-2016), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 52-1 (13-xi-2010), loc. 56 (05-iv-2015), loc. 57 (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-1, loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2016), loc. 67, loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (ovi) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016, 01-iv-2016, 04-iv-2016), loc. 72, loc. 73 (07-xi-2014), loc. 74 (14-iv-2014), loc. 77, loc. 78, loc. 84 (08-xi-2010, 15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-2 (ovi, ex) (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (ex, cop, ovi) (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (ex) (01-iii-2013, 02-iv-2015), loc. 86

***Nesciothemis farinosa* (Förster, 1898)**

Loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 06-xi-2014), loc. 73 (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 81 (03-iv-2015), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015)

***Orthetrum chrysostigma* (Burmeister, 1839)**

Loc. 3 (im, cop), loc. 4 (ex) (10-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 13-iv-2015), loc. 6, loc. 7, loc. 11, loc. 12, loc. 13 (ex), loc. 15, loc. 17 (ex) (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1 (ex), Loc 19-2 (ex), loc. 19-3 pools 1 & 2 (cop, ovi), loc. 21 (te, cop) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 23 (19-iv-2014), loc. 25-1 (ovi), loc. 25-2, loc. 26, loc. 27 (27-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 28, loc. 29 (ex), loc. 30-2, loc. 31 (ex, ovi), loc. 32, loc. 34, loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 41 (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2 (cop, ovi), loc. 43-1 (cop, ovi) (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016, loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 45-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 47 (ex), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 57 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-2, loc. 59, loc. 62 (11-xi-2010), loc. 64 (27-ii-2013, 16-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014), loc. 67, loc. 68 (14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 04-iv-2016), loc. 70 (ex) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 05-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 71, loc. 73 (ex, ovi) (07-xi-2014,

04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013, 14-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014), loc. 75 (cop) (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (cop, ovi) (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 80, loc. 82 (ex) (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 85-2 (ex) (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016)

***Orthetrum ransonnetii* (Brauer, 1865)**

Loc. 2-1 (ovi), loc. 2-2, loc. 5 (ex), loc. 14 (ex), loc. 41 (07-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013), loc. 58-2, loc. 64 (27-ii-2013)

***Orthetrum sabina* (Drury, 1770)**

Loc. 1 (cop), loc. 3, loc. 6 (cop), loc. 10, loc. 11-1 (ex), loc. 11-2 (cop), loc. 13 (ex, cop), loc. 16, loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1 (ex), loc. 19-2 (ex), loc. 19-3 pool 1, loc. 21 (ex, cop, ovi) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 23 (19-iv-2014, 27-x-2014), loc. 24, loc. 27 (27-x-2014), loc. 28, loc. 29 (ex), loc. 31, loc. 36 (cop, ovi), loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1 (ex), loc. 39-2, loc. 40, loc. 41 (cop, ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 42-3, loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44 (cop), loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015), loc. 46, loc. 47 (ex, tan), loc. 49 (11-iv-2014, 30-iii-2016), loc. 50, loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 52-1 (17-iv-2014), loc. 52-2 (17-iv-2014, 05-iv-2016), loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013), loc. 57 (ex) (05-iv-2015), loc. 58-2, loc. 59, loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (04-iv-2016), loc. 67 (16-iv-2014), loc. 68 (14-iv-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (ex, cop) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016, 04-iv-2016), loc. 73 (04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010 27-ii-2013, 14-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 77, loc. 79, loc. 80, loc. 84 (08-xi-2010, 15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (cop, ex, ovi) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (cop, ovi) (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015)

***Pantala flavescens* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Loc. 2-1 (ovi), loc. 3 (ovi), loc. 4 (ovi) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014, 11-x-2014), loc. 5 (ex), loc. 6, loc. 7, loc. 9, loc. 11, loc. 12 (ovi), loc. 13 (ex), loc. 14, loc. 19-1, loc. 19-3 pools 1 & 2, loc. 20, loc. 21 (ex) (26-x-2014), loc. 24 (ex, te), loc. 27 (ex) (27-x-2014), loc. 28 (lar), loc. 29 (ex), loc. 30-1, loc. 36, loc. 37, loc. 41 (07-iv-2016), loc. 42-3, loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 52 (13-xi-2010), loc. 53, loc. 55-1 (12-iv-2014), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 14-iv-2014), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 04-iv-2016), loc. 70 (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014), loc. 76 (03-xi-2014), loc. 77, loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 84

***Rhyothemis semihyalina* (Desjardins, 1832)**

Loc. 56 (05-iv-2015), loc. 60, loc. 61 (04-iv-2016), loc. 62 (ovi) (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2016), loc. 67 (16-iv-2014), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010, 04-iv-2015), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 69-2 (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (tan) (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016, 04-iv-2016), loc. 72, loc. 73 (04-iv-2015), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 77, loc. 82 (04-xi-2014), loc. 83, loc. 84 (ovi) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (tan) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (tan) (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (15-iv-2014)

***Selysiotthemis nigra* (Vander Linden, 1825)**

Loc. 8 (ex), loc. 45-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 70 (13-iv-2014), loc. 85-2 (ten) (15-iv-2014)

***Sympetrum fonscolombii* (Selys, 1840)**

Loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (ovi) (08-iv-2014), loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013)

***Tholymis tillarga* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010)

***Tramea basilaris burmeisteri* Kirby 1889**

Loc. 51 (13-xi-2010, 22-ii-2013), loc. 62 (11-xi-2010), loc. 68 (11-xi-2010), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010), loc. 84

***Tramea limbata* (Desjardins, 1832)**

Loc.64 (07-xi-2014), Loc. 68 (adults gliding and hunting; attempts at oviposition on a car body due to reflected polarised light, 14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (04-iv-2016), loc.73 (07-xi-2014), loc. 75 (31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014), loc. 85-2 (2-iv-2016)

***Trithemis annulata* (Palisot de Beauvois, 1807)**

Loc. 1, loc. 3, loc. 4 (ex) (29-x-2014), loc. 5 (ex), loc. 6 (ex), loc. 7 (ex), loc. 11, loc. 13 (ex), loc. 14 (ex), loc. 15 (ex), loc. 16 (ex), loc. 17 (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1, loc. 19-2 (ex), loc. 19-3 pool 1 (cop, ovi), loc. 21 (ex) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 22, loc. 23 (19-iv-2014, 27-x-2014), loc. 24, loc. 25-1, loc. 25-2, loc. 26, loc. 27 (ex) (27-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 28, loc. 29 (ex), loc. 30-2, loc. 31 (tan), loc. 32, loc. 34, loc. 35, loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 39-2, loc. 41 (ovi) (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 42-3, loc. 43-1 (cop, ovi) (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (cop, ovi) (08-iv-2014, 28-

-iii-2016), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 64 (16-iv-2014), loc. 66 (01-iv-2016), loc. 67 (16-iv-2014), loc. 68 (14-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014), loc. 69-2 (06-xi-2014), loc. 70 (10-xi-2010, 28-ii-2013, 02-iii-2013, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016, 04-iv-2016), loc. 73 (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013, 14-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 79, loc. 80, loc. 81 (03-iv-2016), loc. 84 (15-iv-2014), loc. 85-2 (ex) (02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016)

***Trithemis arteriosa* (Burmeister, 1839)**

Loc. 2-1 (ovi), loc. 2-2, loc. 3 (cop), loc. 4 (ex) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 11-iv-2015, 13-iv-2015, 15-iv-2015), loc. 5 (ex, cop), loc. 6, loc. 7 (te), loc. 9, loc. 10, loc. 12, loc. 13 (ex, ovi), loc. 14, loc. 15, loc. 17 (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18, loc. 19-1 (ex), loc. 19-3 pools 1 & 2 (ex), loc. 20 (cop), loc. 21 (26-x-2014), loc. 22, loc. 23 (19-iv-2014), loc. 24, loc. 25-1, loc. 27 (27-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 31 (ex), loc. 34, loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015), loc. 39-1 (ex), loc. 41 (07-iv-2014, 27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 42-2, loc. 42-3, loc. 43-1 (cop, ovi) (09-iv-2014), loc. 55-1 (23-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 55-2 (24-ii-2013, 12-iv-2014), loc. 57 (ex) (12-iv-2014, 05-iv-2015), loc. 64 (27-ii-2013, 16-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014), loc. 68 (ex) (06-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013), loc. 73 (ex) (04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013, 14-iv-2014, 01-iv-2016), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 79, loc. 80, loc. 81 (ex) (05-xi-2014, 03-iv-2015), loc. 82 (04-xi-2014, 01-iv-2015), loc. 84, loc. 85-2 (ex) (04-xi-2014), loc. 85-4 (ex)

***Trithemis kirbyi* Selys, 1891**

Loc. 4 (11-iv-2015, 13-iv-2015, 15-iv-2015), loc. 5 (ex), loc. 6 (ex), loc. 7 (ex), loc. 11-1 (ex, ovi), loc. 12, loc. 13 (ex), loc. 15 (ex), loc. 16 (ex), loc. 17 (ex) (28-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1, loc. 19-2 (ex), loc. 19-3 pool 2, loc. 20, loc. 21 (ex, cop) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 22, loc. 24, loc. 25-1, loc. 27 (27-x-2014, 10-iv-2015), loc. 28, loc. 30-1, loc. 30-2, loc. 31, loc. 32, loc. 34, loc. 37, loc. 38 (ex) (31-iii-2015), loc. 39-1 (ex), loc. 41 (07-iv-2014), loc. 42-2, loc. 43-1 (09-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-2 (ovi, tan) (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 43-3 (09-iv-2014), loc. 44, loc. 45-1 (08-iv-2014, 28-iii-2016), loc. 45-2 (te) (08-iv-2014), loc. 64 (27-ii-2013), loc. 68 (ex) (04-iv-2015), loc. 73 (ex), loc. 85-2 (15-iv-2014), loc. 85-4 (01-iii-2013)

***Urothemis edwardsii* (Selys, 1849)**

Loc. 68 (ex) (14-iv-2014, 04-iv-2015, 01-iv-2016), loc. 69-1 (11-xi-2010, 03-iii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 04-iv-2016), loc. 70 (te) (13-iv-2014, 06-xi-2014, 05-iv-2015, 31-iii-2016), loc. 72, loc. 81 (03-iv-2016), loc. 84 (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-1 (tan,

ovi) (15-iv-2014, 02-iv-2015, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-2 (ex, cop, ovi) (15-iv-2014, 04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2016), loc. 85-3 (tan) (04-xi-2014, 02-iv-2015), loc. 85-4 (15-iv-2014)

***Urothemis thomasi* Longfield, 1932**

Loc. 4 (ex, ovi) (09-x-2014, 10-x-2014, 11-x-2014, 29-x-2014, 11-iv-2015, 12-iv-2015, 13-iv-2015, 15-iv-2015), loc. 38 (ex, te) (30-iii-2015, 31-iii-2015, 08-iv-2015), loc. 39-1, loc. 41 (ovi) (27-iii-2016, 07-iv-2016), loc. 42-1, loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 44 (cop, ovi), loc. 45-1 (07-iv-2015, 28-iii-2016), loc. 47, loc. 68 (14-iv-2014), loc. 73 (04-iv-2015), loc. 82 (lar, ex) (01-iv-2015), loc. 85-2 (02-iv-2016)

***Zygonyx torridus* (Kirby, 1889)**

Loc. 4 (28-iii-2015, 13-iv-2015), loc. 7 (ex), loc. 12 (ex), loc. 15 (ex), loc. 16, loc. 17 (ex, cop) (28-x-2014), loc. 18 (ex), loc. 19-1 (ex), loc. 19-3 pool 1, loc. 21 (ex, ovi) (26-x-2014, 30-iii-2015), loc. 24, loc. 25-1, loc. 27 (27-x-2014), loc. 28, loc. 34 (cop), loc. 38 (ex) (30-iii-2015), loc. 39-1 (tan), loc. 41 (ex) (07-iv-2014, 07-iv-2016), loc. 43-1 (ovi) (09-iv-2014), loc. 43-2 (08-iv-2014), loc. 44 (ex), loc. 68 (06-xi-2014), loc. 73 (07-xi-2014, 04-iv-2015), loc. 74 (10-xi-2010, 27-ii-2013, 13-iv-2014, 07-xi-2014), loc. 75 (10-xi-2010, 05-xi-2014, 31-iii-2016), loc. 76 (16-iv-2014, 03-xi-2014), loc. 80

Annotations on selected species

Arabicnemis caerulea

This South Arabian endemic was found ranging from single individuals up to groups of nearly 100 adults. Prior to this study, it had only been reported from groups of localities in two disjointed areas: one comprising ca 10 distinct wadi systems in Yemen (WATERSTON 1984; SCHNEIDER & NASHER 2013) and the other situated along the length of the Hajar Mountains (SCHNEIDER 1988; WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997) (Fig. 7). As a result of this paper, we have added nine new wadi systems in the Hajar range, the species appears, therefore, to be common throughout this area. In addition, based on one exuvia, it has been discovered breeding in Dhofar, thus extending one of the two main sub-ranges of the species in Arabia to the East, now identified as the entire Hadramaout. However, it remains unclear whether the species is present continuously to the Hajar range. The species is found in river beds at slow flowing streams and pools between 13 and 889 m a.s.l. (median 284 m, n=73). Algae and dead leaves and shoots were often seen on the water surface and were used by the females to lay their eggs.

Arabineura khalidi

The species is also a South Arabian endemic. Until now it was considered to be restricted to the Hajar Mountains (SCHNEIDER 1988; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1995; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997), where it was known from 17 distinct wadi systems. The present study identified 10 new wadi systems in the Hajar range, where the species can now be regarded as common over this whole area (Fig. 8). Moreover, two mature individuals were found in the Dhofar at the Ayun pools (loc. 81) in November 2014 and one probable teneral was observed at the Hasik waterfall (loc. 57), where the species remains to be confirmed. These records extend the range of *A. khalidi* considerably as far as southern Arabia, suggesting that it may have a scattered distribution further west towards Yemen, similar to *Arabicnemis caerulea*. Altitudinal distribution ranges between 20 and 810 m a.s.l. (median 323 m, $n = 86$). Records usually refer to smaller groups of less than 10 individuals per locality, only exceptionally to larger groups of *ca* 100 or even 200 individuals (loc. 41). The species' mesohabitat appears to be similar to that of *A. caerulea*, although the former seems more rheophile. Females were seen ovipositing in groups in dead plant material such as leaves or roots.

Agriocnemis pygmaea

This widespread Oriental species extends to the Muscat area in northern Oman (SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997) and southern Oman in the Dhofar (REIMER 2009; WIPRÄCHTIGER 2010; BALL 2014; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). Only three localities have so far been identified in the Dhofar, all at or near sea level. No new localities were found during our surveys. This species favours mats of abundant and dense riparian grassy vegetation (Cyperaceae, Juncaceae etc.) forming marshy areas around lagoons, near-coastal ponds and pools. It tolerates slightly brackish waters. Abundances show high variation between years: at loc. 70 up to 100 individuals were present in April 2015; however, even after a number of hours of intensive searching by two persons, only one individual was observed at the same site in April 2016.

Azuragrion nigradorsum

The south-eastern African species (DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014) shows a restricted distribution in South Arabia, where it is confined to Yemen,

Figure 7. Distribution map of *Arabicnemis caerulea* in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman. Red dots indicate records taken during our surveys 2010–2016, grey dots indicate records before year 2000 and crosses records from the year 2000 to 2017 from other studies. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

Figure 8. Distribution map of *Arabineura khalidi* in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman. Red dots indicate records taken during our surveys 2010–2016, grey dots indicate records before year 2000 and crosses records from the year 2000 to 2017 from other studies. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

including Socotra, and the Dhofar tropical pocket. Our observations confirm its occurrence as a string of populations along the southern slopes and sea margins of the Dhofar mountains and hills. Nine distinct localities with 17 recording spots are known, including four new localities. *Azuragrion nigradorsum* inhabits densely vegetated coastal and sub-coastal lagoons and pools as well as small pools in mountain brooks with variable amounts of vegetation (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; VAN DER WEIDE & KALKMAN 2008; REIMER 2009; BALL 2014; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). The species is found between sea level and *ca* 300 m a.s.l., (median 125 m, n=17) mostly in groups of up to 20 individuals. In one locality (loc. 64) there was a population in excess of 100 individuals.

Azuragrion somalicum

Similar to *A. nigradorsum*, this Horn of Africa species shows a restricted distribution in South Arabia, where it is also confined to Yemen, including Socotra (SCHNEIDER & NASHER 2013), and the Dhofar tropical pocket. Our observations confirm its occurrence as a string of isolated populations along the southern slopes of the Dhofar mountains between 30 and 685 m a.s.l. (median 200 m, n=13). Presently eight distinct localities including 13 recording spots are known, including one new sighting (loc. 58) (WATERSTON 1980; WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; VAN DER WEIDE & KALKMAN 2008; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). The species is found in large and small well-vegetated wadi pools, where the floating vegetation appears to be used for oviposition. The melanic form described as *A. s. amitinum* Waterston (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991) was dominant, but a single individual of the blue form (*A. s. somalicum*) was recorded (ÉD) within a more melanic population at loc. 58-2, suggesting that colour variation reflects rather intraspecific variability than actual subspeciation. The validity of this subspecies has been already questioned by SCHNEIDER & NASHER (2013).

Ceriagrion glabrum

This African species is widespread south of the Sahara and extends to the southern half of the Arabian Peninsula (SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; FEULNER 1999; DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014; SCHNEIDER & SAMRAOUI 2015;

BOUDOT et al. 2016a) over its western, southern and eastern sub-coastal mountain ranges, avoiding true deserts. Former records along the lower Nile River in Egypt have not been confirmed in recent years and the species is believed to be extinct there. Beyond Yemen and western Saudi Arabia, this species is widespread in South Arabia in the Hajar and the Dhofar from sea level to 700 m a.s.l. (median 109 m, n=54). It is found in more or less vegetated wadis and well-vegetated wadi pools and coastal lagoons, where sufficient vegetation is present on the banks (grasses, rushes, Cyperaceae) to allow the females to lay eggs.

Pseudagrion decorum

The main range of this Oriental species is centred on India, from where it extends to neighbouring countries. To the west it reaches Iran, the UAE and southern Oman (SCHNEIDER 1988; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; FEULNER 1999; MITRA 2013). Taking into account all available data from southern Arabia, the species ranges there from sea level to 800 m. a.s.l. (median 190 m, n=64) and is common in the Hajar, whereas it is confined to few localities along the southern slopes and foothills of the Dhofar Mountains and hills in south Oman. As *P. decorum* has been found only 25 km from the Yemen border (BALL 2014), it is reasonable to expect that it occurs in eastern Yemen as well. The species is found in wadis, wadi pools and coastal lagoons where there is sufficient vegetation on the banks to allow the females to lay eggs.

Pseudagrion sublacteum

This African species extends to southern Arabia in Yemen, where it is widespread, and Oman in the Dhofar, where it is confined to a small area (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; VAN DER WEIDE & KALKMAN 2008; REIMER 2009; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). Six recording spots in five distinct localities are known, ranging from 85 to 205 m a.s.l. (median 147 m, n=6), among which two are new. The species is confined to running water with macrophytes used for endophytic oviposition.

Anax imperator

Many individuals (but not all) of this species show a different habitus in comparison to the European populations and have an entirely brown tho-

rax, which poses identification difficulties in the field and may lead to confusion with *A. parthenope*, particularly in the case of females. Male abdominal appendages are however typical for *A. imperator* and differ strongly to those of other European, African or Asian *Anax* species. Hence this variation is to be ascribed to intraspecific variability rather than to significant speciation. This species is known from sea level to 1 950 m a.s.l. (median 212 m, n = 144).

Lindenia tetraphylla

The core range of this species lies in Central Asia, the Middle East and the Balkans (SCHORR et al. 1998; DE KNIJF et al. 2013). In the Mediterranean it is well established in mainland Italy and Sardinia with a few additional localities in the Maghreb. It was formerly known in the Iberian Peninsula, where it is now extinct (KALKMAN & BOGDANOVIĆ 2015). *Lindenia tetraphylla* is the only gomphid known to migrate (SCHNEIDER 1981) and to breed in stagnant waters and even temporary ponds (SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997). The combination of these factors and the availability of many new man-made habitats in the Mediterranean accounts for the success of this species, allowing the extension of its initial range (BROCHARD & VAN DER PLOEG 2013; DE KNIJF et al. 2013; HAMZAOUI et al. 2015). Nevertheless, most of South Arabian records are in line with its natural habitat preferences and the species has been found in northern Oman in the Hajar and its foothills (16 distinct localities) and in the Dhofar (two distinct localities). All 18 localities range between 20 and 685 m a.s.l. (median 104 m) and refer to stony and variably vegetated wadis and wadi ponds and pools.

Paragomphus sinaiticus

The species extends from the central Sahara to Iran with populations scattered over most of the sub-coastal mountains of the Arabian Peninsula in Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Oman and the United Arab Emirates (BOUDOT et al. 2013). In South Arabia, the main aggregate of localities remains in the Hajar range, but records from southern Oman (REIMER 2009; WIPRÄCHTIGER 2010; this study) show the species to be found additionally along the southern slopes of the Dhofar mountains and hills.

Its close relative, *P. genei*, is restricted to the Hajar range and is apparently regionally much more scarce. Although DUMONT (1991) considered *P. sinaiticus* a species of stagnant waters, we found it both in pools in the beds of rivers from just a few meters wide to 40 × 500 m in size, and in slow flowing streams between 13 and 800 m a.s.l. (median 300 m, n = 79). Due to this type of habitat and its range, it is sometimes found syntopic with *P. genei*.

Crocothemis sanguinolenta

This African perennial stream dweller is widespread south of the Sahara and extends to the Arabian Peninsula (DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014; SCHNEIDER & SAMRAOUI 2015; BOUDOT et al. 2016b) over its western, southern and eastern sub-coastal mountain ranges, avoiding true deserts. Another disjunct area is known from the tropical enclave of the Dead Sea in Jordan (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER 1982; DIJKSTRA & DINGEMANSE 2000). Beyond the Yemen and southwestern Saudi Arabia, this species is known in Arabia from the Hajar and the Dhofar, from sea level to 1 610 m a.s.l. (median 212 m, n = 43). It reproduces in permanent high flowing wadis and their pools but vagrants may be found elsewhere.

Macrodiplax cora

This tropical Asian and Australasian species extends over southern Asia, Australia and a variety of isolated Indian and Pacific Oceans Islands. Due to its vagrant and migratory behaviour, it has also been recorded in the South of the Arabian Peninsula in Yemen, including Socotra, and Oman, where it has established resident populations on the southern and north-eastern coasts. Further west it has even reached Somalia and has colonized the north-eastern coast of South Africa in Kwazulu-Natal (DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014). *Macrodiplax cora* is known to be found primarily in brackish waters and the records obtained during this study not only confirm that it is mostly observed at lagoons, mangroves, estuaries, and coastal and sub-coastal pools, but also suggest that it may develop at inland desert water bodies as well (loc. 51 in 2010 and 2013). All Omani resident and vagrant individuals were observed at 26 distinct localities and 50 recording spots, mostly at low elevations from sea level to 200 m a.s.l. (median 9 m, n = 50).

Nesciothemis farinosa

This African species is widespread south-east of an African diagonal running from Luanda in Angola to the Nile Delta (DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014). Beyond the Red Sea, it is known from the south-western Saudi Arabian Mountains, Yemen and Oman (SCHNEIDER & KRUPP 1993; LAMBRET & BOUDOT 2009; BOUDOT et al. 2016c). In Oman it is confined to the Dhofar tropical pocket (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; VAN DER WEIDE & KALKMAN 2008; BALL 2014; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a) and known from only seven distinct localities (10 recording spots) ranging from 10 to 685 m a.s.l. (median 205 m, n = 10). The species is usually encountered as single to small numbers of individuals in preferably well-vegetated habitats. However, it also appears to do well in channelled and paved head waters modified for recreational activities.

Orthetrum ransonnetii

This eremic species extends from Mauritania (DURAND & RENOULT 2012) and Morocco (JUILLERAT & MONNERAT 2009; BOUDOT & DE KNIJF 2012) over Algeria, Niger and Chad (DUMONT 1978a, 1978b, 2014) to the Arabian Peninsula, particularly to the Hajar Mountains, and Iran (HEIDARI & DUMONT 2002; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016b). It is regionally known from 20 to 736 m a.s.l. in the UAE and Oman (median 284, n = 39). We not only found the species at several localities in the Hajar Mountains but also in the southern Dhofar region. Oviposition and exuviae were observed in running waters throughout the year. The species favours strongly arid and extremely rocky and stony environments, where the larvae subsist the dry season in residual pools in the beds of wadis (JUILLERAT & MONNERAT 2009; BOUDOT & DE KNIJF 2012). A female was seen ovipositing in a ca 2 m² and 20 cm deep, muddy and stony pool, covered with algae. Exuviae were collected at pools of similar characteristics.

Rhyothemis semihyalina

In the Arabian Peninsula this mostly sub-Saharan species is strictly confined to the Dhofar tropical pocket (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997), with 22 distinct localities and 39 recording spots from sea level to 205 m a.s.l. (median 10, n = 39). It has been assessed as »Endan-

gered« on the regional Arabian Red List (SCHNEIDER & SAMRAOUI 2015). This Afrotropical dragonfly occurred until recently at two other disjunct localities: one in north-eastern Algeria and the other in northern Israel, where it has disappeared due to the drainage of the former Lake Hula. The populations in Dhofar are now the only remaining outside tropical Africa. In the region, its best localities are represented by the coastal lagoons and sub-coastal swampy springs, ponds and pools where it is seasonally common. *Rhyothemis semihyalina* prefers marshy areas with well-developed vegetation of herbs.

Selysiothemis nigra

This species is widely scattered from Central Asia and north-western India across entire Arabia and the Sahara to the westernmost Mediterranean countries. In the Mediterranean, many recently discovered localities refer to man-made habitats such as irrigation ponds and dammed reservoirs, thus increasing the number of populations and favouring the dispersion and establishment of the species. Beyond Yemen, most of the South Arabian records cluster in northern Oman and the UAE (TOURENQ et al. 2005; WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997; RÄZ & WIPRÄCHTIGER 2012; FEULNER & JUDAS 2013; SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a). *Selysiothemis nigra* is known to be migrant and vagrant and the rather small number of records in the region (30 from 22 colonies in 20 distinct localities) suggests that the small number of records of reproduction point to a transient rather than stable population. The species was observed at dams, ponds, pools, coastal lagoons and terrestrial habitats without water in desert, urban and vegetated habitats, from sea level to 374 m a.s.l. (median 25 m, n = 22), either in swarms (FEULNER & JUDAS 2013) or – as observed in this study – in very low numbers of one or two individuals.

Tholymis tillarga

This species ranges from Australia, Asia and some Pacific islands to Africa (CLAUSNITZER 2011) and is a powerful migrant (FRASER 1956; SCHNEIDER 1992). Our record of two individuals observed at close distance in reed beds on 11-xi-2010 at the coastal Khor Rawri (loc. 69-1) constitutes the first actual observations for the entire Arabian Peninsula. A subsequent record by

BALL (2014) in April 2014 at another sub-coastal wadi pool suggests that this species occurs more frequently in South Arabia than expected and that it was overlooked due to its crepuscular activity, making it cryptic during the day (FRASER 1956; CORBET 1962; DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014).

Whether a reproducing population exists in the Dhofar tropical pocket as suggested by BALL (2014), based on the record of a male and of an ovipositing female, or whether all recorded individuals are migrants or vagrants, can only be demonstrated by repetitive, intense searching during twilight hours and at night. The status of the species in the region can, however, be assessed with high probability by an analysis of meteorological and migrating events. Our November 2010 record corresponds with a massive influx of migrant species in the eastern part of the Arabian Peninsula. In the UAE, numerous *Pantala flavescens* and *Anax ephippiger* were reported between September 2010 and January 2011 (B. Reimer pers. comm.) with the first records of *T. basilaris* (as Indian ssp. *burmeisteri*) for the Emirates dating from November 2010 (REIMER 2011). During the November 2010 visit to southern Oman, *P. flavescens* and *A. ephippiger* were found in every locality visited, including the Empty Quarter desert. The most impressive swarms were localized along the Dhofar coastline and comprised mixed flocks of several thousand individuals at dusk. The unusually large number of the melanic subspecies *T. b. burmeisteri* suggests a multispecies migration of Indian origin. Each autumn, millions of dragonflies migrate from southern India to Africa across the Indian Ocean with a stopover in the Maldives archipelago. Although *P. flavescens* is the main species, other species including *T. tillarga* are also involved in reasonable numbers (ANDERSON 2009). Hence, the status of *T. tillarga* in the region is most likely connected to sporadic immigration linked to monsoon events. This might result in attempted or successful reproduction in the Dhofar.

Tramea basilaris

First records of *T. basilaris* in Oman and the UAE date back to 1977 (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991), with subsequent records in 1992 (SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997) and 2010 (REIMER 2011; this study). Most of these observations ranged from sea level to 215 m a.s.l. (median 85 m, n = 11) and were said to be part of migrating swarms of various species of dragonflies.

It is probable that *T. basilaris* is mainly a migrant of Indian origin in Arabia, where it was also found in south-west Saudi Arabia (SCHNEIDER & KRUPP 1993). Whether it has established temporary or long lasting breeding populations in the region has not yet been established.

Tramea limbata

In the Arabian Peninsula, this Afro-Indian species seems to be restricted to the southern and central parts of Oman where populations are regularly recorded in coastal areas such as lagoons, springs, ponds and pools on mountain foothills in the Dhofar region. The species was found between sea level and 305 m a.s.l. (median 15 m, n = 16) and spends much of the day hovering and taking advantage of thermal air currents in the Dhofar. Many *Tramea* records which have not allowed identification to species level due to this hovering behaviour high above ground possibly pertain to *T. limbata*, which breeds in the Dhofar region.

Urothemis edwardsii

In the Arabian Peninsula this Afrotropical species is strictly confined to the Dhofar tropical region (11 distinct localities and 23 colonies-known so far), where it was assessed as »Endangered« on the regional Arabian Red List (SCHNEIDER & SAMRAOUI 2015). Another disjunct population occurs in north-eastern Algeria (SAMRAOUI 2017) whereas another former disjunct population in northern Israel has now become extinct due to the drainage of Lake Hula. *Urothemis edwardsii* is most abundant at ponds, pools and lagoons in the coastal area where it can be quite common between sea level and 685 m a.s.l. (median 13 m, n = 23). Depending on the season, 10 to 50 adults were observed in these localities. This species prefers marshy areas with well-developed vegetation of low and tall herbs and low bushes.

Urothemis thomasi

Distribution. This species was for a long time regarded as confined to Somalia and Oman, particularly the Dhofar region and the north-eastern part of the country (LONGFIELD 1932; NIELSEN 1957; SCHNEIDER 1988). Ten localities have been hitherto published from Dhofar, of which some are probably extinct due to the drastic modifications of the primary habi-

tats for recreational use. Several unpublished records exist from the Dhofar and in the southern Hajar range (C. Monnerat pers. comm.; M. Waldhauser in 'observation.org'; E. Cowan in 'www.allodonata.com'). It is only recently that the species was found in the UAE in WWNP (FEULNER & JUDAS 2013), where it is now regularly observed and is obviously resident (occurrence of exuviae). The species now is distributed from the Horn of Africa to the Dhofar, Al-Wusta and to the southern and northern Hajar range in a string of 21 quite distinct localities (Fig. 9). Some catchments include several sub-locations and 44 recording spots are currently known in total. In Fujairah, the WWNP locality includes three distinct headwater stretches where the species appears to be well established. In addition, in north-eastern Oman, for example at Al Amirat (loc. 38), Wadi As Shab (loc. 41) and Wadi Tiwi (loc. 42), the species reproduces at several pools in each wadi, which are connected by slow running water. Wadi Tiwi and Wadi As Shab are only 4 km apart and even the sub-locations in Wadi Bani Khaled (loc. 43) are a maximum of 28 km distance from Wadi Tiwi, suggesting that the species is well settled in this area, with a possible metapopulation functioning. In the Dhofar, the Wadi Darbat (loc. 68) and Khor Rawri (loc. 69) form part of the same watershed and the spots where the species was found are certainly connected by vagrant individuals.

Two of the oldest known populations – recorded 1930 at the type locality Ayn Razat (loc. 75; LONGFIELD 1932; SCHNEIDER 1988) and 1978 at Ayn Sahalnaut (loc. 76; WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991) – appear to be extinct due to recent habitat management for human recreational activities including channeling and construction of concrete or stony pavements. Accordingly, localities show a considerable decrease in the number of species observed and it is unlikely that *U. thomasi* has survived there and emphasising the vulnerability of the species. Other localities where the species has not recently been recorded include Wadi Abyad (loc. 26), Ras Shuwaymiya (loc. 55), Khor Rawri (loc. 69), Ayn Razat (loc. 75 and Ayn Sahalnaut (loc. 76). All these localities appear to be in reasonable condition and the species may still be present. On the other hand, the four new localities discovered during our 2014–2016 surveys – Wadi Dayqah (loc. 39), Sayq (loc. 44), Ayn Fulayj (loc. 45) and Ayn Tabraq (loc. 73) – with that of the Al Wusta coastal desert (loc. 47: Ayn Najir) suggest that the species may be found in additional lo-

calities with a wider range of ecological features. It is even possible that the old Thumrait oasis record from 1978 (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991) may be more than a vagrant individual as previously assumed.

Phenology. All available records of *U. thomasi* range from mid-March to early December including all months in between with the exception of August and September. However spring records (March–June, $n = 35$) are more than twice the Summer/Autumn records (July–December, $n = 16$), suggesting some seasonality; however, this may be partly also due to the timing of the surveys.

Abundance. Although more widely distributed than previously known, *U. thomasi* was found in small numbers ranging from one to ten individuals in every locality (both adults and exuviae) and appears to be a fairly rare species.

Ecology and behaviour. The species was found more often at lentic wadi pools (86%, $n = 14$) than at clearly lotic wadi stretches. The area of these pools was variable, ranging from *ca* 7 m² to *ca* 1.5 ha. Loc. 47 and loc. 73 were exceptions as at these localities the pools were of very variable sizes, ranging from 1.5 × 5 to 35 × 450 m. The substrate of *U. thomasi* habitats typically comprised mud, gravel and stones but also organic matter. Usually, banks were colonised by well-developed and tall vegetation consisting of *Typha* and *Phragmites*, especially at places where breeding evidence was recorded (Fig. 6), but also by grasses, rushes and sedges. Observed copulae took place within such vegetation (loc. 44). We observed two unguarded ovipositing females: one by the shade of *Phragmites*, just above their roots and the other just below some small bushes and sparse *Phragmites*. Exuviae were found a few centimetres above the water surface, either on rocks or emerging plants. One F-1 larva collected from a pool near Salalah (loc. 82) was successfully reared until emergence in an aquarium. The substrate at this location was a clayey – silty mud with stones and dead organic material. The micro-habitat of other localities where we found exuviae was similar. This suggests a relation to the calm and well-vegetated waters that the adults seem to prefer.

Urothemis thomasi has hitherto been found from sea level to 650 m a.s.l. (median 190 m, $n = 44$). Taking account only of the localities where reproduction was evidenced or likely, this species appears to breed in waters with

Figure 9. Distribution map of *Urothemis thomasi* in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman. Red dots indicate records taken during our surveys 2010–2016, grey dots indicate records before year 2000 and crosses records from the year 2000 to 2017 from other studies. Map background source © Google™ Earth Service (WGS84/PM)

a salt content of 0.53, 0.56 and 1.14 PSU, which is close to the middle regional salinity range (0.1–9.27 PSU, median 0.31, $n = 58$; see Appendix 1). We found a male on a perch at a desert brackish brook on the 06-iv-2015 (loc. 47; conductivity 18.32 mS/cm, corresponding to a salinity of 9.27 PSU at 32.5°C) which would match the probable habitat of the species in the Thumrait desert oasis record (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991). COWAN & COWAN (2017) also found the species at the same pond, suggesting a possible autochthony in the Al Wusta region.

Males were seen more often than females (41♂ vs 5♀). They perched above the water bodies on twigs, stems or overhanging rocks, whereas other, presumably satellite males, remained at ground level. Territoriality was observed during some hours at two sites with the resident male flying up to chase a newcomer and returning within a minute. Three times, we noticed a male ‘arriving’ at the pond in the morning hours shortly after the first sunrays had appeared. The two ovipositing females were observed laying by sequential single water touches every 2–3 sec. During rearing, the larva typically sat motionless between stones or under a dead branch waiting for prey, suggesting a slow style of life (JOHANSSON 2000). It was fed with more mobile larvae of Zygoptera, young *Anax* sp. and Libellulidae.

Zygonyx torridus

This Afro-Indian species is widespread in sub-Saharan Africa (DIJKSTRA & CLAUSNITZER 2014) and with disjunct smaller areas in the Maghreb, southern Europe, Anatolia, the Levant, Iran and the coastal mountains of the Arabian Peninsula. Its Indo-Pakistani range is large but valid records are in such small numbers there (FRASER 1924, 1936; SINGH & PRASAD 1976; BABU & NANDY 2010; NAIR 2011), that the species is often reputed to be very rare in this area (SINGH & PRASAD 1976; NAIR 2011). Our records confirm its wide distribution in the sub-coastal mountains of Oman and the Emirates. So far, 33 distinct localities have been brought on record in the Hajar range and the Dhofar between 20 and 890 m a.s.l. (median 254 m, $n = 54$).

The specimens from Oman and the UAE we examined agree with most of those from Western Africa, Namibia and South-Africa (e.g., SUHLING & MARTENS 2007; TARBOTON & TARBOTON 2015), although they were darker than most of those from Morocco. In fact there is a strong variability in ab-

domen melanism and wing colouration, which range from clear to slightly yellowish or slightly smoky, over the whole Africa and the Mediterranean. Wings from south Arabian individuals are clear or only slightly tinted yellowish and there is no reason to ascribe the regional populations to the so-called melanic subspecies, *Z. t. isis* Fraser, 1924. The latter is considered a doubtful taxon (KUNZ et al. 2006) with strongly amber-coloured wings (see NAIR 2011), as recently claimed (SCHNEIDER & IKEMEYER 2016a).

Conclusion and outlook

As already emphasized by WATERSTON & PITTAWAY (1991) and SCHNEIDER (1988), the Odonatofauna of the south-eastern Arabian peninsula combines several zoogeographic components and includes wide ranging subcosmopolitan, endemic or near endemic species. In addition, African species, Oriental (Indomalayan) and some Irano-Turanian species, which are eremic, are found in the region. The present surveys increased our knowledge of the distribution of the various Odonata species found, particularly in the Hajar, the Dhofar and Al Wusta. *Ischnura evansi*, *I. senegalensis*, *Anax imperator*, *Crocothemis erythraea*, *Urothemis thomasi* and *Macrodiplax cora* are new to Al Wusta. *Arabicnemis caerulea*, *Arabineura khalidi* and *Tramea basilaris* are new to the Dhofar.

Important differences were noticed in the present species composition of some localities in comparison with former inventories (WATERSTON & PITTAWAY 1991; SCHNEIDER & DUMONT 1997). In some cases, such changes may be ascribed to habitat degradation resulting from management for places of recreation for local people and tourism. In cases where the habitats are not so strongly altered, population dynamics linked to nomadism and natural habitat instability are certainly important parameters, with high flow episodes able to change significantly important wadi structures. On the other hand, the species list has increased for many other localities, thanks to the recent sampling effort increase (more dragonfly enthusiasts, more logistic facilities, etc.) and to a better knowledge of the species due to new field-guides and web portals.

Further developments will need Odonata exuviae as this allows the study of resident reproductive communities. Such implementation will take a while, however, as identification of regional exuviae presents inherent prob-

lems on account of the very limited information published. In the present work, we have relied heavily upon the key by SUHLING et al. (2014), which covers many of the African species present in Arabia although it was based on research in Namibia. Considerable care should be taken during identification to prevent confusion with other African and Oriental species, for which little documentation is available. As a result of the present surveys a great deal of information has been provided so that it is now possible for one of us (DC) to identify all species of Anisoptera currently known from South and East Arabia; e.g., the larva and exuvia of *U. thomasi* has been described for the first time (CHELMICK et al. 2016). As to the Zygoptera, more research is needed, including laboratory breeding to obtain living larvae so that a correct identification can be provided after emergence of the adults. It is hoped that these documents and information will encourage the regional naturalists to take a strong interest to their wetlands and to identify both adults and exuviae, the latter by collecting.

Acknowledgements

We are sincerely grateful to His Highness General Sheikh Mohamed bin Zayed Al Nahyan and to the Mohamed bin Zayed Species Conservation fund for the grant which made possible the 2014 and 2015 missions. We also wish to warmly acknowledge the entire Wadi Wurayah National Park team, especially the director Olivier Combreau for his administrative support, as well as the rangers Ali Kakembo Swamiti and Sami Majid for their assistance in the field. Phil Benstead accompanied GDK at some localities during spring 2016 in Dhofar and Heidi Demolder and Isha De Knijf helped us during the spring 2014 and spring 2016 field trip. Patricia Martin Cabrera contributed to the rearing of an *U. thomasi* larvae in the lab and to field records. Thanks are due to Klaas-Douwe B. Dijkstra, Gary Feulner, Tony Pittaway and the late Bob Reimer for sharing their extensive knowledge relative to the wildlife of the Middle East, and especially Henri J. Dumont and Wolfgang Schneider who accepted to review an earlier version of the manuscript.

References

- ANDERSON C.R. 2009. Do dragonflies migrate across the western Indian Ocean? *Journal of tropical Ecology* 25: 347-358
- BABU R. & NANDY S. 2010. New Odonata records from Himachal Pradesh, India. *Notulae odonatologicae* 7: 55-57

- BALL L. 2014. An investigation of odonate communities within Wadi Sayq, Dhofar Province, Oman (Insecta: Odonata). *Check List* 10: 857-863
- BOUDOT J.-P. 2006. *Urothemis thomasi*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2006: e.T22817A9389959. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2006.RLTS.T22817A9389959.en>
- BOUDOT J.-P. & DE KNIJF G. 2012. Nouvelles données sur les Odonates du Maroc oriental et méridional (Odonata). *Martinia* 28: 1-28
- BOUDOT J.-P., CLAUSNITZER V., DIJKSTRA K.-D.B., SUHLING F., SAMRAOUI B. & SCHNEIDER W. 2013. *Paragomphus sinaïticus*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2013: e.T16110A13373413. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: www.iucnredlist.org
- BOUDOT J.-P., CLAUSNITZER V., DIJKSTRA K.-D.B., SUHLING F., SCHNEIDER W. & SAMRAOUI B. 2016a. *Ceriagrion glabrum*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T59828A75380384. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: www.iucnredlist.org
- BOUDOT J.-P., CLAUSNITZER V., SCHNEIDER W., SUHLING F., DIJKSTRA K.-D.B. & SAMRAOUI B. 2016b. *Crocothemis sanguinolenta*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T59860A84816724. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: www.iucnredlist.org
- BOUDOT J.-P., CLAUSNITZER V., SUHLING F., DIJKSTRA K.-D.B., SAMRAOUI B. & SCHNEIDER W. 2016c. *Nesciothemis farinosa*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T59921A83853056. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: www.iucnredlist.org
- BROCHARD C. & VAN DER PLOEG E. 2013. Searching for exuviae of endemic Odonata species in Greece. *Brachytron* 15: 83-101
- CHAVAGNAC V., CEULENEER G., MONNIN C., LANSAC B., HOAREAU G. & BOULART C. 2013a. Mineralogical assemblages forming at hyper-alkaline warm springs hosted on ultramafic rocks: A case study of Oman and Ligurian ophiolites. *Geochemistry Geophysics Geosystems* 14: 2474-2495
- CHAVAGNAC V., MONNIN C., CEULENEER G., BOULART C., HOAREAU G. 2013b. Characterization of hyperalkaline fluids produced by low-temperature serpentinization of mantle peridotites in the Oman and Ligurian ophiolites. *Geochemistry Geophysics Geosystems* 14: 2496-2522
- CHELMICK D.G., SEIDENBUSCH R., BOUDOT J.-P. & BROCHARD C. 2016. The exuviae of the Urothemistinae of the Arabian Peninsula including the first description of the exuvia and final instar larva of *Urothemis thomasi* Longfield 1932 (Odonata: Libellulidae). *Tribulus* 24: 97-108
- CLAUSNITZER V. 2011. *Tholymis tillarga*. In: IUCN 2012. IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2012.2. Online on the internet, URL [06-iv-2013]: www.iucnredlist.org
- CORBET P.S. 1962. A biology of dragonflies. Witherby, London
- COWAN E.M. & COWAN P.J. 2013. The dragonflies and damselflies of a wadi pool near Nizwa, northern Oman, 2012-2013. *Tribulus* 21: 14-23
- COWAN E.M. & COWAN P.J. 2015. Odonata (Insecta) at a wadi Pool near Nizwa, northern Oman. *Journal of threatened Taxa* 7: 7538-7546. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.11609/JoTT.o4207.7538-46>
- COWAN E.M. & COWAN P.J. 2017. The Odonata (Insecta) of northern and central Oman. *Journal of threatened Taxa* 9: 10776-10791. doi:<http://doi.org/10.11609/jott.3230.9.10.10776-10791>

- DE KNIJF G., VANAPPELGHEM C. & DEMOLDER H. 2013. Odonata from Montenegro, with notes on taxonomy, regional diversity and conservation. *Odonatologica* 42: 1-29
- DIJKSTRA K.-D.B. & CLAUSNITZER V. 2014. The dragonflies and damselflies of eastern Africa: handbook for all Odonata from Sudan to Zimbabwe. Studies in Afrotropical Zoology 298. Royal Museum for Central Africa, Tervuren
- DIJKSTRA K.-D.B. & DINGEMANSE N.J. 2000. New records of *Crocothemis sanguinolenta* Burmeister, 1839) from Israel, with a critical note on the subspecies *arabica* Schneider, 1982. *International Journal of Odonatology* 3: 169-171
- DUMONT H.J. 1978a. Odonata from Niger with special reference to the Ad'r Mountains. *Revue zoologique africaine* 92: 303-316
- DUMONT H.J. 1978b. Odonates d'Algérie, principalement du Hoggar et d'oasis du Sud. *Bulletin et Annales de la Société royale belge d'Entomologie* 114: 99-106
- DUMONT H.J. 2014. Odonata from the Tibesti Mountains and the Ounianga Lakes in Chad, with notes on *Hemianax ephippiger* accumulating in the desert. *Odonatologica* 43: 13-24
- DUMONT H.J. 1991. Fauna Palaestina. Insecta V – Odonata of the Levant. The Israel Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Jerusalem
- DURAND É. & RENOULT J.-P. 2012. Addition à l'odonatofaune de l'Adrar mauritanien. *Poiretia, la Revue naturaliste du Maghreb* 4: 7-16
- FEULNER G.R. 1999. Two new UAE damselflies: *Ceriagrion glabrum* and *Pseudagrion decorum*. *Tribulus* 9: 31
- FEULNER G.R. & JUDAS J. 2013. First UAE records of two Odonata: the dragonfly *Urothemis thomasi* and the damselfly *Ischnura nursei*. *Tribulus* 21: 4-13
- FEULNER G.R., REIMER R.W. & HORNBY R.J. 2007. Updated and illustrated checklist of dragonflies of the UAE. *Tribulus* 17: 37-62
- FRASER F.C. 1924. A survey of the odonate (Dragonfly) fauna of Western India with special remarks on the genera *Macromia* and *Idionyx* and descriptions of thirty new species. *Records of the Indian Museum* 26: 423-522, pls. XXV-XXVII
- FRASER F.C. 1936. The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Odonata, Vol. 3. Taylor & Francis, London
- FRASER F.C. 1956. Faune de Madagascar. Insectes. Odonates Anisoptères. Publications de l'Institut de Recherche Scientifique, Tananarive-Tsimbazawa
- GILES G.B. 1998. An illustrated and annotated checklist of the dragonflies of the UAE. *Tribulus* 8: 9-15
- HAMZAOUI D., HAFIANE H.M., MEBARKI M., ARAB A., ALFARHAN A. & SAMRAOUI B. 2015. The Gomphidae of Algeria and the Maghreb: status, ecology and conservation (Insecta: Odonata). *International Journal of Odonatology* 18: 175-191
- HEIDARI H. & DUMONT H.J. 2002. An annotated check-list of the Odonata of Iran. *Zoology in the Middle East* 26: 133-150
- JOHANSSON F. 2000 The slow-fast life style characteristics in a suite of six species of odonate larvae. *Freshwater Biology* 43: 149-159
- JUILLERAT L. & MONNERAT C. 2009. Odonata in southern Morocco, with first records of *Orthetrum ransonnetii* and *Sympetrum sinaiticum* (Odonata: Libellulidae). *Libellula* 28: 97-115

- KALKMAN V.J. & BOGDANOVIĆ T. 2015. *Lindenia tetraphylla* (Vander Linden, 1825) In: Boudot J.-P. & Kalkman V.J. (Eds), Atlas of the European dragonflies and damselflies: 197-199. KNNV Uitgeverij, Zeist
- KUNZ B., OBER S.V. & JÖDICKE R. 2006. The distribution of *Zygonyx torridus* in the Palaearctic (Odonata: Libellulidae). *Libellula* 25: 89-108
- LAMBRET P. & BOUDOT J.-P. 2009. *Nesciothemis farinosa* (Förster, 1898) et *Orthemis ransonnetii* (Brauer, 1865) nouveaux pour l'Arabie Saoudite et autres observations d'odonates sur les reliefs côtiers de la Mer Rouge. *Martinia* 25: 153-155
- LONGFIELD C. 1932. A new species of the genus *Urothemis* from southern Arabia, and some comments on the species of Odonata inhabiting the Qara Mountains. *Stylops* 1: 34-35
- MITRA A. 2013. *Pseudagrion decorum*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2013: e.T167269A17536286. Online on the internet, URL [20-ii-2017]: www.iucnredlist.org
- NAIR M.V. 2011. Dragonflies & damselflies of Orissa and eastern India. Wildlife Organisation, Forest & Environment Department, Government of Orissa, Bhubaneswar
- NIELSEN C. 1957. Missione del Prof. Giuseppe Scortecci in Migiurtinia col contributo del Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche. VI. Odonata. *Annali del Museo civico di Storia naturale di Genova* 69: 31-35
- RÄZ K. & WIPRÄCHTIGER P. 2012. Oman 2012 trip report. Libellen – Dragonflies – Libellules. Trip report. Online on the internet, URL [23-x-2017]: <http://www.naturus.ch/downloads/bericht-2012-trip-report.doc>
- REIMER R.W. 2009. Additional records for Oman. *Agrion* 13: 45-47
- REIMER R.W. 2011. *Tramea basilaris* (Beauvais [sic], 1817) new to UAE. *Agrion* 15: 22-23
- REIMER R.W., FEULNER G.R. & HORNBY R.J. 2009. Errata and addenda: Updated checklist of dragonflies of the UAE – including a third species of *Ischnura* damselfly. *Tribulus* 18: 28-36
- SAMRAOUI B. 2017. The hand of man or Santa Rosalia's blessing? A rebuttal of the paper "on the restoration of the relict population of a dragonfly *Urothemis edwardsii* Selys (Libellulidae: Odonata) in the Mediterranean". *Journal of Insect Conservation*, doi:10.1007/s10841-017-9966-2
- SARGEANT D., ERIKSEN H. & ERIKSEN J. 2008. Birdwatching guide to Oman. 2nd ed. Al Roya Publishing, Muscat
- SCHNEIDER T. & IKEMEYER D. 2016a. Dragonflies of Oman – a revised illustrated checklist (Odonata). *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 126: 137-147
- SCHNEIDER T. & IKEMEYER D. 2016b. Records of dragon- and damselflies from Khorasan-e-Razavi and Khorazn-e-Shomali in North-east-Iran (Odonata). *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 126: 211-216
- SCHNEIDER W. 1981. Eine Massenwanderung von *Selysiothemis nigra* (van der Linden, 1825) (Odonata: Macrodiplactidae) und *Lindenia tetraphylla* (van der Linden, 1825) (Odonata: Gomphidae) in SüdJordanien. *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 91: 97-103
- SCHNEIDER W. 1982. *Crocothemis sangui-nolenta arabica* n. subsp., ein afrikanisches Relikt in der südlichen Levante. *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 92: 25-31
- SCHNEIDER W. 1988. Dragonflies (Odonata) of the Wahiba Sands and adjacent Areas, Eastern Oman. *Journal of Oman Studies Special Report* 3: 377-388

- SCHNEIDER W. 1992. *Anax tristis* Hagen, 1867 (Aeshnidae) and *Tholymis tillarga* (Fabricius, 1798) (Libellulidae) recorded from off Angola. *Fragmenta Entomologica* 23: 243-246.
- SCHNEIDER W. & DUMONT H.J. 1995. *Arabineura* n. gen., a new Protoneurid genus from Arabia, with the description of the hitherto unknown female of *Arabineura khalidi* (Schneider, 1988) comb. nov. (Insecta: Odonata: Protoneuridae). *Biologisch Jaarboek Dodona* 62 [1994]: 114-120
- SCHNEIDER W. & DUMONT H.J. 1997. The dragonflies and damselflies (Insecta: Odonata) of Oman. An updated and annotated checklist. *Fauna of Saudi Arabia* 16: 89-110
- SCHNEIDER W. & KRUPP F. 1993. Dragonfly records from Saudi Arabia, with an annotated checklist of the species from the Arabian Peninsula (Insecta: Odonata). *Fauna of Saudi Arabia* 13: 63-78
- SCHNEIDER W. & NASHER A.K. 2013. Dragonflies from mainland Yemen and the Socotra Archipelago – additional records and novelties. *International Dragonfly Fund-Report* 57: 1-13
- SCHNEIDER W. & SAMRAOUI B. 2015. The status and distribution of dragonflies and damselflies (Odonata) in the Arabian Peninsula. Chapter 5. In: García N., Harrison I., Cox N. & Tognelli M.F. (Eds), The status and distribution of freshwater biodiversity in the Arabian Peninsula: 39-55. IUCN, Gland, Cambridge, Arlington
- SCHORR M., SCHNEIDER W. & DUMONT H.J. 1998. Ecology and distribution of *Lindenia tetraphylla* (Insecta, Odonata, Gomphidae): a review. *International Journal of Odonatology* 1: 65-88
- SINGH A. & PRASAD M. 1976. Odonata of Doon Valley – I. Anisoptera. *Records of the Zoological Survey of India* 70: 21-38
- SUHLING F. & MARTENS A. 2007. Dragonflies and damselflies of Namibia. Gamsberg Macmillan Publishers, Windhoek
- SUHLING F., MÜLLER O. & MARTENS A. 2014. The dragonfly larvae of Namibia (Odonata). *Libellula Supplement* 13: 5-106
- TARBOTON W. & TARBOTON M. 2015. A guide to the dragonflies and damselflies of South Africa. Struik Nature, Cape Town
- TOURENQ C., BARCELO I, KUMARI A. & DREW C. 2005. The terrestrial mammals, reptiles and invertebrates of Al Wathba wetland reserve – A species list and status report. Terrestrial Environment Research Centre, Abu Dhabi
- VAN DER WEIDE M.J.T. & KALKMAN V.J. 2008. Some new records of dragonflies from Oman. *Agrion* 12: 52-54
- WATERSTON A.R. 1980. Insects of Saudi Arabia. Odonata. *Fauna of Saudi Arabia* 2: 57-70
- WATERSTON A.R. 1984. A new genus and species of platycnemidid dragonfly from the Arabian Peninsula (Zygoptera). *Odonatologica* 13: 139-146
- WATERSTON A.R. & PITTAWAY A.R. 1991. The Odonata or dragonflies of Oman and neighbouring territories. *Journal of Oman Studies* 10 [1989]: 131-168
- WIPRÄCHTIGER P. 2010. Oman trip report Libellen – Dragonflies – Libellules. Online on the internet, URL [23-x-2017]: <http://www.naturus.ch/downloads/trip-report-libellen-komprimiert.pdf>

Appendix 1

Water characteristics recorded at different localities in the United Arab Emirates and the Sultanate of Oman during the EWS-WWF surveys in autumn 2014 and spring 2015. OR – over range. Localities printed in bold denote those where *Urothemis thomasi* was found.

		Temp. [°C]	pH	Cond. [mS/cm]	TDS [ppm]	[Salt] [PSU]
1	Wadi Bih	32.0	8.62	0.566	401	275
2	Wadi Al Lahbah					
	pool 1	25.2	11.77	6.540	4630	3550
	pool 2	26.8	8.38	1.883	1340	955
3	Wadi Abadilah					
	pool 1	29.6	8.38	0.777	552	381
	pool 2	33.7	9.39	0.570	406	277
4	Wadi Wurayah					
	pool above the waterfall	23.7	8.35	0.608	432	310
	pool downhill the gorges	22.9	8.77	0.491	348	240
	pool above the gorges	27.5	8.64	0.526	325	241
5	Al Khulaybiyah	25.6	9.30	0.343	244	165
7	Wadi Al Madha					
	pool 1	28.3	8.72	0.518	310	251
	pool 2	29.9	8.47	0.520	359	252
	pool 3	32.2	8.64	0.410	292	199
11	Hatta					
	site 1	27.3	8.64	3.550	2530	1870
	site 2	26.7	8.92	3.000	2120	1540
12	Wadi Qhafi					
	stream enlargement	30.5	8.94	0.489	347	240
	pool	29.8	8.14	0.481	342	233
13	Subaitah Oasis					
	retention basin	26.6	9.22	0.443	315	215
	pool	28.5	8.85	0.443	314	215
14	Sayyah					
	pool	31.1	9.05	0.897	635	441
	white pool	31.5	10.80	0.680	483	330
15	Wadi Khamis	28.5	8.66	0.714	511	351
16	Fazah	31.4	8.13	1.117	795	551
17	Hayl Ra'sah					
	pool	27.7	8.70	0.832	590	408
	stream	31.0	9.90	0.861	611	438
18	Ghuzayn					
	stream	34.9	8.97	1.034	735	510
	pool	34.0	7.88	1.062	754	524
19	Ghab					
	site 1	31.1	8.48	1.022	742	502
	site 2, pool 1	25.6	8.59	0.547	286	264
	site 2, pool 2	28.6	9.31	0.525	372	255
20	Hajir	33.0	8.77	0.525	374	256
21	Hawqayn					
	wadi pool	30.6	8.35	0.885	636	441
	terrace pool	27.5	8.16	0.834	592	409

		Temp. [°C]	pH	Cond. [mS/cm]	TDS [ppm]	[Salt] [PSU]
22 Iqd an Nizuh		30.3	8.36	0.797	565	390
23 Rustaq hot spring		45.3	7.24	0.978	799	483
24 At Tabaqah		30.8	7.95	0.831	589	408
27 Qilal		32.7	8.60	0.840	593	412
28 Ad Dif		29.2	7.97	0.733	519	357
31 Ar Rissah		27.5	9.54	0.210	151	104
32 Bahla		29.6	8.74	2.230	1570	1190
38 Wadi Aday		31.8	8.20	2.16	1510	1140
39-1 Wadi Dayqah	stream	27.0	8.55	0.638	453	320
	pool	29.0	8.47	0.643	454	328
44 Sayk		26.7	8.09	1.100	780	562
45-1 Wadi Musawi		30.2	8.19	2.380	1720	1280
47 Ayn Najir	stream	32.5	8.01	18.320	OR	9270
	pool	27.1	7.57	13.250	9340	7890
48 Khor Ras Madrakah		29.8	8.48	OR	OR	OR
50 Water station		26.6	8.69	7.88	5560	4510
56 Wadi Sana'ak		32.8	8.07	7.160	5080	4110
57 Natif waterfall		31.6	8.66	1.520	1080	802
68 Wadi Darbat		30.0	8.50	0.671	477	341
70 Khor Taqah		28.2	7.47	9.210	6400	5280
73 Ayn Tabraq		29.2	8.15	0.613	435	310
81 "Ayun pools"		22.9	8.26	1.422	1010	737
82 Ayn Ishat		30.9	8.40	0.751	583	531
85 Al Mughsayl	pool 1	30.5	7.05	5.290	3820	2960
	pool 2	32.8	8.55	4.040	2880	2240
	pool 3	34.0	9.04	6.020	4230	3450
	lagoon	35.7	9.20	13.370	9440	8100

